

ENDURE

Inequalities, Community Resilience, and
New Governance Modalities in a Post-Pandemic World

Survey Data Codebook Complete Edition

Kristinn Már Ársælsson and Peter Ramand

Countries: Brazil • Croatia • Germany • Poland • United Kingdom • United States

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The ENDURE Project

This research was conducted as part of ENDURE (Inequalities, Community Resilience and New Governance Modalities in a Post-Pandemic World), a Trans-Atlantic Platform project examining the short- and long-term consequences of the COVID-19 crisis. ENDURE brings together researchers from eleven countries across the Americas and Europe to study how the pandemic has affected inequality, governance, and social resilience. The project is led by Dr. Mihai Varga at Freie Universität Berlin with Soner Barthoma as project coordinator. The survey was designed by Peter Ramand and Kristinn Már Ársælsson and administered by Qualtrics in Croatia, Poland, Germany, the UK and the US, and by Netquest in Brazil.

The survey component was funded in six countries by their respective national science agencies: Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft-Germany (DFG, Grant nr. 495747738); National Science Centre Poland (UMO-2021/03/Y/HS6/00167), the Economic and Social Research Council, (ESRC-UK, Grant nr. ES/X000788/1); Croatian Science Foundation (Grant nr. 090-18-04/22-18-03/01); FAPESP - Brazil (Grant nr. 2021/07839-2), and the United States National Science Foundation (NSF, Grant nr. NSF-SBE/SMA #2219400) under the Trans-Atlantic Platform RRR Call 2021, project “ENDURE: Inequalities and social resilience and new governance in a post-pandemic world”.

This codebook is developed as part of the survey report “[Politics After the Pandemic: Attitudes to Democracy, Authoritarianism, Protest and the "Culture War" Across Six Countries](#)” (2026), and presents findings from Endure/Cluster 3, which uses survey methods to examine political attitudes and mobilization in comparative perspective.

Citation

Please cite the dataset as follows when quoting or re-using it:

Ársælsson, K. M., Ramand, P., Barthoma, S., Buzinkic, E., Selo Sabic, S., Cardoso, A., Gitahy, L. Karolak, M., Pieńkowski, P., Varga, M., Jones, E. C., & Foley, J. (2026). *ENDURE Survey Datasets*. Endure/Zenodo. DOI. 10.5281/zenodo.20306487

Reuse disclaimer

The ENDURE Survey Datasets are made available for research and teaching purposes. Users may download, analyse, and quote from the data provided they:

- Acknowledge the dataset using the citation above.
- Do not attempt to re-identify individual respondents.
- Respect any ethical or legal restrictions described in the accompanying documentation.

By using these data, you agree that the authors and their institutions bear no responsibility for interpretations or analyses based on secondary use of the dataset.

Overview

This codebook documents all variables in the ENDURE merged survey dataset (see the related [Public datasets](#), and see also the related [Survey Descriptive Report](#)).

The survey was fielded in six countries: Brazil, Croatia, Germany, Poland, the United Kingdom, and the United States from December 2024 to February 2025. Respondents were recruited by Qualtrics in all countries except Brazil, where data was collected by Netquest in October and November 2024. See the public datasets

The codebook is organized by country. The United States section serves as the master reference, documenting all variables including those available only in specific countries. Each subsequent country section presents question text and response labels in the original language as administered to respondents. The structural framing (section headers, notes, and display logic) remains in English throughout.

The merged dataset contains one row per respondent across all six countries. Variables that appear only in certain countries are blank for countries where they do not apply.

Sample Sizes and Data Quality

In the five countries where data was collected via Qualtrics (Croatia, Germany, Poland, UK, USA), Qualtrics applied quality checks to flag respondents identified as poor quality (e.g., speeding, bot-like behavior) and whether respondents passed one of two attention checks (see details below). The variable gc codes respondent quality: gc = 1 indicates respondents who passed Qualtrics' quality checks. Other values indicate respondents flagged for potential quality issues. This quality filtering was not applied in Brazil, where data collection was handled by Netquest.

The table below shows sample sizes after quality check filtering (gc = 1) alongside total respondent counts.

Country	Quality Check Sample (gc=1)	Total Respondents
Brazil	N/A (Netquest)	2047
Croatia	1600	7290
Germany	2094	10244
Poland	2086	15745
UK	2109	10035
USA	2161	9423

Attention Checks

Two attention check questions were embedded in the survey (variables attention1 and attention2). These are instructional manipulation checks designed to identify respondents who are not carefully reading question text. Both checks present what appears to be a straightforward question but embed a directive within the instructions that asks respondents to override the obvious response.

The first check (attention1) asks respondents to select words describing how they are currently feeling from a list of 20 emotions. However, the instructions above the list ask respondents to ignore the question and instead select only "None of the above." The second check (attention2)

asks respondents about their favorite newspaper sections. The instructions ask respondents to select only “Classified” and “None of the above,” ignoring the question itself.

These checks are generally considered difficult, as they require respondents to read the full instructions rather than responding to the surface-level question. For this reason, only one of the two checks was required to pass the quality check. Attention checks were not administered in Brazil, where data was collected by Netquest using a different protocol.

Block Randomization

To minimize order effects, question blocks were randomized within two groups. The first group randomized the presentation order of six blocks: People-Centrism, Anti-Elitism, Manicheanism, Trust in Institutions (feeling thermometer), Nationalism, and Attitudes Towards Democracy. The first attention check was included as the final item in this group.

The second group randomized the order of eleven blocks: Ideology (all four scales), Authoritarian Attitudes, Civil Society, Political Mobilization, Degrowth (UK only), Political Interest and Voting, Life Satisfaction and Alienation, Neighborhood Perception, Economic Perceptions, Cultural Issues (sexual harassment, ethnic diversity), and COVID-19 and Vaccination. The second attention check was included as the final item in this group.

Blocks within each group appeared in a different random order for each respondent, but the two groups themselves were always presented in the same sequence: the first group was always administered before the second. Demographics and Social Class questions were presented last, in a fixed order, and were not randomized.

In addition, within each attitude block, the order of individual items was also randomized. For example, the trust in institutions thermometer items appeared in a different order for each respondent, as did the items within the nationalism, people-centrism, anti-elitism, Manicheanism, and authoritarian attitudes batteries.

Stratification and Derived Variables

Respondents were stratified by age, gender, and education to improve sample representativeness. Qualtrics assigned derived variables to manage the stratification quotas. These variables appear in the data for all countries where Qualtrics administered the survey (all countries except Brazil):

Gender_Assigned: Gender category used for stratification quota management.

AgeScore: Numeric age group code used for stratification.

AgeGroup: Age band label (e.g., 18–24, 25–34, 35–44, 45–54, 55–64, 65+).

Education: Harmonized education level (Low, Mid, High). Note: the USA version uses five levels (Low, Mid1, Mid2, High1, High2) rather than three.

The variable gc is a Qualtrics quality control flag. gc = 1 indicates respondents who passed quality checks (e.g., not flagged for speeding or bot-like response patterns). See the Sample Sizes section above for details.

Missing Data

Qualtrics’ “force response” option was enabled for all substantive items: respondents could not advance without providing an answer. A “Prefer not to answer” option was included for each item; if selected the response was marked as missing in the data export.

Blank cells in the data may indicate:

(a) The respondent selected “Prefer not to answer.”

(b) The respondent dropped out before reaching the question.

(c) The question was not shown due to skip logic (applies to follow-up items such as harass2, methnic2, die2, vacrisk2, etc.).

These sources of missingness are not explicitly coded in the data. No special numeric codes are used; missing data are represented by empty cells.

Cross-Country Notes

Country-specific political variables: The USA includes pol_id, pol_d, pol_r, pol_pres. The UK includes brexit. European countries (Croatia, Germany, Poland) include eu.

Mobilization items differ: mobi_3 appears in Brazil and UK; mobi_6 appears in Croatia, Germany, Poland, and USA.

Trust thermometer th_pre_8 (EU): Not included in the Brazil or USA data.

Degrowth items (dg*, em*): Available only in the UK data.

Germany includes mig (migration background) and edu2 (vocational qualifications).

The Brazil aligned file maps the Brazil-specific instrument onto the common cross-country variable schema. A separate Brazil Public file with the full Brazil-specific instrument is available.

United States (Master)

Master Reference — English (U.S.)

Language: English

Data Source: Qualtrics

Sample: 2,161

This section documents all variables in the merged dataset using U.S. English question wording. Country availability is noted for each variable.

United States (Master)

Survey Metadata

StartDate

Available in: Croatia, Germany, Poland, UK, USA

EndDate

Available in: Croatia, Germany, Poland, UK, USA

Duration..in.seconds.

Available in: All countries

consent

Available in: Croatia, Germany, Poland, UK, USA

Question: *This survey is about organizations, COVID-19, politics, and civic engagement. Your participation will help us to better understand opinions about these issues. You are not required to answer any of the following questions and can decide at any point to withdraw from the survey. Your answers will be anonymous. We appreciate your time and thank you for giving thoughtful and honest answers to each of the questions in this important survey.*

Value	Label
1	I AGREE to participate in the survey
2	I DECLINE to participate

Demographics

gender

Available in: All countries

Question: *What is your gender?*

Respondents who select “Other” are prompted to provide an open-text response, stored in gender_4_TEXT (All countries).

Value	Label
1	Male
2	Female
3	Non-binary
4	Other

age

Available in: All countries

Question: *How old are you?*

Value	Label
1	18
2	19
3	20
...	<i>(value = age - 17)</i>
75	92
76	93
83	100
93	Prefer not to answer

Note: Coding follows the pattern value = age - 17 (e.g., 1 = 18 years old, 50 = 67 years old). The value 93 is reserved for “Prefer not to answer” and should be treated as missing.

edu

Available in: All countries. Education categories differ by country. Country teams determined their own response options. The values shown below are from the U.S. instrument. See companion codebooks for country-specific categories and original-language labels.

Question: *What is the highest level of education you have completed?*

Value	Label
1	Less than high school
2	High school
3	Vocational education
4	Some college
5	Bachelor's degree
6	Master's degree
7	PhD or other postgraduate qualification

ethnicity

Available in: Brazil, Croatia, Poland, UK, USA. Question wording and response categories differ by country. This is a multi-select question; respondents who selected multiple options have comma-separated values. The values shown below are from the U.S. instrument. See companion codebooks for country-specific wording and categories.

Question: *What is your race or ethnicity? Select all that apply.*

Respondents who select “Other” are prompted to provide an open-text response, stored in ethnicity_2_TEXT, ethnicity_6_TEXT, ethnicity_7_TEXT, ethnicity_15_TEXT (Croatia, USA, UK, Poland).

Value	Label
1	White

2	Black / African American
3	Latino / Latina / Latinx
4	American Indian / Alaska native
5	Asian
6	Other

live

Available in: All countries

Question: *Where do you live?*

Respondents who select “Other” are prompted to provide an open-text response, stored in live_3_TEXT, live_4_TEXT (Croatia, Germany, Poland, UK, USA).

Value	Label
1	An urban area (e.g., a city or town)
2	A suburb
3	A rural area
4	Other

born

Available in: Croatia, Germany, Poland, UK, USA

Question: *Were you born in the USA?*

Respondents who select “No (not born in country)” are prompted to provide an open-text response, stored in born_2_TEXT (Poland).

Value	Label
1	Yes
2	No

reg

Available in: Croatia, Germany, Poland, UK, USA. Region/state categories are country-specific. The USA uses U.S. states; the UK uses broad regions; other countries use their own regional classifications. Germany includes an additional region variable (reg2). The Brazil aligned file does not contain region data; however, the Brazil Public file includes state (born_UF) and city (born_city) variables. See companion codebooks for country-specific categories.

Question: *Which state do you live in?*

Value	Label
1	Alabama
2	Alaska
3	Arizona

4	Arkansas
5	California
6	Colorado
7	Connecticut
8	Delaware
9	Florida
10	Georgia
11	Hawaii
12	Idaho
13	Illinois
14	Iowa
15	Kansas
16	Kentucky
17	Louisiana
18	Maine
19	Maryland
20	Massachusetts
21	Michigan
22	Minnesota
23	Mississippi
24	Missouri
25	Montana
26	Nevada
27	New Hampshire
28	New Jersey
29	New Mexico
30	New York
31	North Carolina
32	North Dakota
33	Ohio
34	Oklahoma
35	Oregon
36	Pennsylvania
37	South Carolina
38	South Dakota
39	Tennessee

40	Texas
41	Utah
42	Vermont
43	Virginia
44	Washington
45	West Virginia
46	Wisconsin
47	Wyoming
49	Indiana
50	Nebraska
51	Rhode Island

socecon**Available in:** All countries**Question:** *What best describes your current work situation?*

Value	Label
1	30 hours a week or more
2	Less than 30 hours a week
3	Self-employed
4	Retired / pensioned
5	Homemaker not otherwise employed
6	Student
7	Unemployed
8	Disabled

relig_imp**Available in:** Croatia, Germany, Poland, UK, USA**Question:** *How important is religion in your life?*

Value	Label
1	Not at all important
2–9	(...)
10	Very important

relig_dom

Available in: All countries

Question: *Do you belong to a religion or religious denomination?*

Value	Label
1	Yes
2	No

relig_dom2

Available in: All countries

Question: *Which religious denomination do you belong to?*

Respondents who select “Other” are prompted to provide an open-text response, stored in relig_dom2_7_TEXT, relig_dom2_8_TEXT, relig_dom2_11_TEXT (Germany, Croatia, UK, USA, Poland).

Display logic: Displayed if relig_dom = 1 (respondent belongs to a religion or religious denomination).

Value	Label
1	Roman Catholic
2	Protestant
3	Orthodox (Russian, Greek, etc.)
4	Jewish
5	Muslim
6	Hindu
7	Buddhist
8	Other

house

Available in: All countries

Question: *Which of the following best describes your housing situation?*

Value	Label
1	I own my own house
2	I rent
3	I live with family or friends
4	I am currently unhoused

inc_alt

Available in: All countries. Response categories use country-specific currencies and income brackets. The USA and UK report income annually; Germany and Poland report monthly. See companion codebooks for country-specific versions.

Question: Below is a list of INCOMES. We would like to know your HOUSEHOLD INCOME. In other words, before taxes, what is the combined income of all earners in your household from all sources, including wages, salaries, pensions or any other form of income.

Value	Label
1	A) Less than \$9999 per year
2	B) \$10,000 to \$14,999 per year
3	C) \$15,000 to \$19,999 per year
4	D) \$20,000 to \$24,999 per year
5	E) \$25,000 to \$29,999 per year
6	F) \$30,000 to \$39,999 per year
7	G) \$40,000 to \$49,999 per year
8	H) \$50,000 to \$59,000 per year
9	I) \$60,000 to \$99,999 per year
10	J) \$100,000 to \$149,999 per year
11	K) \$150,000 or more per year

Populist Attitudes: People-Centrism

Do you agree or disagree with the following statements?

Scale: 1 = Strongly disagree, 2 = Disagree, 3 = Neither agree nor disagree, 4 = Agree, 5 = Strongly agree.
Prefer not to answer was offered but excluded from export.

Available in: All countries

Variable	Item
peoplec_pre_1	Politicians should always listen closely to the problems of the people.
peoplec_pre_2	Politicians don't have to spend time among ordinary people to do a good job.
peoplec_pre_3	The will of the people should be the highest principle in this country's politics.

Populist Attitudes: Anti-Elitism

Do you agree or disagree with the following statements?

Scale: 1 = Strongly disagree, 2 = Disagree, 3 = Neither agree nor disagree, 4 = Agree, 5 = Strongly agree.
Prefer not to answer was offered but excluded from export.

Available in: All countries

Variable	Item
antie_pre_1	The government is pretty much run by a few big interests looking out for themselves.
antie_pre_2	Government officials use their power to try to improve people's lives.

antie_pre_3	Quite a few of the people running the government are crooked.
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Populist Attitudes: Manicheanism

Do you agree or disagree with the following statements?

Scale: 1 = Strongly disagree, 2 = Disagree, 3 = Neither agree nor disagree, 4 = Agree, 5 = Strongly agree.
Prefer not to answer was offered but excluded from export.

Available in: All countries

Variable	Item
manich_pre_1	You can tell if a person is good or bad if you know their politics.
manich_pre_2	The people I disagree with politically are not evil or bad people.
manich_pre_3	The people I disagree with politically are just misinformed.

Trust in Institutions (Feeling Thermometer)

How would you rate the following groups and organizations? Ratings between 51 degrees and 100 degrees mean that you feel favorable and warm toward the group or organization. Ratings between 0 degrees and 49 degrees mean that you feel negatively about this group/organization. Rate the group at the 50-degree mark if you don't feel particularly warm or cold toward them. If you do not recognize a group or institution, click "prefer not to answer."

Scale: 0–100 feeling thermometer (0 = cold/unfavorable, 50 = neutral, 100 = warm/favorable). Prefer not to answer was offered but excluded from export.

Variable	Item	Countries
th_pre_1	Journalists	All countries
th_pre_4	Scientists	All countries
th_pre_5	University professors	All countries
th_pre_6	Civil servants	All countries
th_pre_7	Congress / Parliament	All countries
th_pre_8	The European Union (EU)	Croatia, Germany, Poland, UK
th_pre_9	Political parties	All countries
th_pre_10	Major companies	All countries
th_pre_11	Capitalists	All countries
th_pre_12	The police	All countries
th_pre_13	The military	All countries
th_pre_16	NATO	Croatia, Germany, Poland, UK, USA
th_pre_17	The International Monetary Fund (IMF)	All countries

th_pre_18	Rich people	All countries
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Nationalism

Some people say the following things are important to be truly American. Others say they are not important. How important do you think each of the following is?

Scale: 1 = Very important, 2 = Fairly important, 3 = Not very important, 4 = Not important at all. Prefer not to answer was offered but excluded from export.

Available in: All countries

Variable	Item
nat_pre_1	To have been born in the USA
nat_pre_2	To have American ancestry
nat_pre_3	To be able to speak English
nat_pre_4	To share American culture

Attitudes Towards Democracy

dem_pre

Available in: All countries

Question: *How important is it for you to live in a country that is governed democratically? On this scale where 1 means “not at all important” and 10 means “absolutely important,” what position would you choose?*

Value	Label
1	Not at all important
2–9	(...)
10	Absolutely important

Below are descriptions of various types of political systems. For each one, would you say it is a very good, fairly good, fairly bad, or very bad way of governing your country?

Scale: 1 = Very good, 2 = Fairly good, 3 = Fairly bad, 4 = Very bad. Prefer not to answer was offered but excluded from export.

Available in: All countries

Variable	Item
polsys_pre_1	Having a strong leader who does not have to bother with congress and elections
polsys_pre_2	Having experts, not government, make decisions according to what they think is best for the country
polsys_pre_3	Having the army rule the country

polsys_pre_4

Having a democratic political system

Political Orientation and Ideology

ideol_self

Available in: All countries

Question: *In political matters, people talk of ‘the left’ and ‘the right’. How would you place your views on this scale generally speaking?*

Value	Label
1	The left
2–9	(...)
10	The right

ideol_respo

Available in: All countries

Question: *How would you place your views on this scale?*

Value	Label
1	Individuals should take more responsibility for providing for themselves
2–9	(...)
10	The state should take more responsibility to ensure that everyone is provided for

ideol_eq

Available in: All countries

Question: *How would you place your views on this scale?*

Value	Label
1	Incomes should be made more equal
2–9	(...)
10	There should be greater incentives for individual effort

ideol_own

Available in: All countries

Question: *How would you place your views on this scale?*

Value	Label
1	Private ownership of business and industry should be increased
2–9	(...)

10	Government ownership of business and industry should be increased
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eu

Available in: Croatia, Germany, Poland. This item was asked only in European countries. English wording shown here is translated from the Croatian instrument. Note: Croatia uses a 5-point categorical scale; Germany and Poland use a 1–10 scale. See companion codebooks for country-specific wording and response formats.

Question: *Some say European Union enlargement should go further. Others say it has already gone too far. What is your opinion?*

Value	Label
1	Should go much further
2	Should go a little further
3	Should remain as it is
4	EU has already expanded more than necessary
5	Further expansion would be far too much

brexit

Available in: UK

Question: *How did you vote in the Brexit referendum in 2016?*

Value	Label
1	I voted to LEAVE the European Union (EU)
2	I voted to REMAIN in the European Union (EU)
3	I did not vote

Authoritarian Attitudes

How much do you agree or disagree with the following statements?

Scale: 1 = Strongly disagree, 2 = Disagree, 3 = Neither agree nor disagree, 4 = Agree, 5 = Strongly agree.
Prefer not to answer was offered but excluded from export.

Available in: All countries

Variable	Item
al_1	Young people today don't have enough respect for traditional values
al_2	Schools should teach children to obey authority
al_3	People who break the law should be given stiffer sentences

Political Mobilization

Have you ever engaged in any of the following forms of political action? Please tell us if you have engaged in any of these, would engage in any of these, or would never engage in any of these.

Scale: 1 = Have done, 2 = Would do, 3 = Would never do. Prefer not to answer was offered but excluded from export.

Variable	Item	Countries
mobi_1	Sign an electronic petition	All countries
mobi_2	Join a boycott	All countries
mobi_3	Boycott / deliberately buy products for ethical or political reasons	Brazil, UK
mobi_4	Attend a lawful demonstration	All countries
mobi_6	Participate in a strike	Croatia, Germany, Poland, USA

Political Interest and Voting

pol_i

Available in: All countries

Question: *How interested would you say you are in politics?*

Value	Label
1	Very interested
2	Somewhat interested
3	Not very interested
4	Not at all interested

pol_vote

Available in: All countries. Voting options are country-specific, reflecting national parties and electoral systems. See companion codebooks for country-specific response options.

Question: *If there were a national election tomorrow, for which party on this list would you vote? Respondents who select "Other" are prompted to provide an open-text response, stored in pol_vote_5_TEXT (USA).*

Value	Label
1	The Democratic Party
2	The Republican Party
3	The Green Party
4	The Libertarian Party
5	Other

pol_id**Available in:** USA**Question:** *Generally speaking, do you usually think of yourself as a Democrat, a Republican, an independent, or what?**Respondents who select “Other” are prompted to provide an open-text response, stored in pol_id_4_TEXT (USA).*

Value	Label
1	Republican
2	Democrat
3	Independent
4	Other party

pol_d**Available in:** USA**Question:** *Would you call yourself a strong Democrat or not a very strong Democrat?**Display logic: Displayed if pol_id = 1 (respondent identifies as a Democrat).*

Value	Label
1	Strong Democrat
2	Not a very strong Democrat

pol_r**Available in:** USA**Question:** *Would you call yourself a strong Republican or not a very strong Republican?**Display logic: Displayed if pol_id = 2 (respondent identifies as a Republican).*

Value	Label
1	Strong Republican
2	Not a very strong Republican

pol_pres**Available in:** USA**Question:** *In the 2024 Presidential Election, did you vote for Kamala Harris, Donald Trump, or another candidate?*

Value	Label
1	Kamala Harris
2	Donald Trump
3	Did not vote

5	Other presidential candidate
---	------------------------------

Satisfaction and Alienation

sat

Available in: All countries

Question: *All things considered, how satisfied are you with your life as a whole these days?*

Value	Label
1	Dissatisfied
2–9	(...)
10	Satisfied

alien

Available in: All countries

Question: *Some people feel they have completely free choice and control over their lives, and other people feel that what they do has no real effect on what happens to them. Please use the scale to indicate how much freedom of choice and control you feel you have over the way your life turns out?*

Value	Label
1	None at all
2–9	(...)
10	A great deal of control

cap

Available in: All countries

Question: *To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statement? In my daily life I get very little chance to show how capable I am.*

Value	Label
1	Strongly disagree
2	Disagree
3	Neither agree nor disagree
4	Agree
5	Strongly agree

Neighborhood Conditions

How frequently do the following things occur in your neighborhood?

Scale: 1 = Extremely often, 2 = Fairly often, 3 = Rarely, 4 = Never. Prefer not to answer was offered but excluded from export.

Available in: All countries

Variable	Item
hood_1	Robberies
hood_2	Alcohol consumption in the streets
hood_3	Sexual harassment

Economic Perceptions

econ

Available in: All countries. Question wording is country-specific. See companion codebooks for country-specific versions.

Question: *What do you think about the state of the economy these days in the United States? Would you say the state of the economy is good, neither good nor bad, or bad?*

Value	Label
1	Good
2	Neither good nor bad
3	Bad

econg

Available in: All countries

Question: *How good would you say the state of the economy is?*

Display logic: Displayed if econ = 1 (respondent said economy is good).

Value	Label
1	Somewhat good
2	Very good
3	Extremely good

econb

Available in: All countries

Question: *How bad do you think the state of the economy is?*

Display logic: Displayed if econ = 3 (respondent said economy is bad).

Value	Label
1	Somewhat bad
2	Very bad

3	Extremely bad
---	---------------

fsit**Available in:** All countries**Question:** *So far as you and your family are concerned, how worried are you about your current financial situation?*

Value	Label
1	Not at all
2	A little
3	Moderately
4	Very
5	Extremely

Sexual Harassment Attitudes**harass****Available in:** All countries**Question:** *Do you think attention to sexual harassment has gone too far, has not gone far enough, or has been about right?*

Value	Label
1	Has gone too far
2	Has been about right
3	Has not gone far enough

harass2**Available in:** All countries**Question:** *Do you think attention to sexual harassment has gone a little too far, or much too far?*
Display logic: Displayed if harass = 1 (respondent said attention has gone too far).

Value	Label
1	Has gone a little too far
2	Has gone much too far

harass3**Available in:** All countries**Question:** *Do you think attention to sexual harassment has not gone quite far enough, or not nearly far enough?**Display logic: Displayed if harass = 3 (respondent said attention has not gone far enough).*

Value	Label
1	Has not gone quite far enough
2	Has not gone nearly far enough

Immigration and Ethnic Relations

methnic

Available in: All countries

Question: *Does increasing the number of people of different races and ethnic groups in the U.S. make this country a better place to live, a worse place to live, or does it make no difference?*

Value	Label
1	Better
2	Makes no difference
3	Worse

methnic2

Available in: All countries

Question: *Does increasing the number of people of different races and ethnic groups make the U.S. a little better place to live, or a lot better place to live?*

Display logic: Displayed if methnic = 1 (respondent said diversity makes country better).

Value	Label
1	A little better
2	A lot better

methnic3

Available in: All countries

Question: *Does increasing the number of people of different races and ethnic groups make the U.S. a little worse place to live, or a lot worse place to live?*

Display logic: Displayed if methnic = 3 (respondent said diversity makes country worse).

Value	Label
1	A little worse
2	A lot worse

mig

Available in: Germany. This item was asked only in Germany.

Question: *Sind Ihre beiden Eltern in Deutschland geboren?*

mig2**Available in:** Germany**Question:** *Würden Sie sich selbst als Migrant:in bzw. Person mit Migrationshintergrund bezeichnen?***COVID-19 and Vaccination****cov****Available in:** All countries**Question:** *Were you infected with COVID-19 between 2020 and 2022?*

Value	Label
1	Yes
2	No

vac**Available in:** All countries**Question:** *Have you been vaccinated against COVID-19?*

Value	Label
1	Yes
2	No

die**Available in:** All countries**Question:** *Did any of your family members die as a direct result of COVID-19 between 2020 and 2022?*

Value	Label
1	Yes
2	No

die2**Available in:** Croatia, Germany, Poland, UK, USA**Question:** *How many of your family members died as a direct result of COVID-19 between 2020 and 2022?**Display logic: Displayed if die = 1 (respondent said yes, a family member died of COVID).*

Value	Label
1	1
2	2

3	3
4	4
5	5 or more

vacrisk**Available in:** All countries**Question:** *Do the health benefits of vaccinations generally outweigh the risks, do the risks outweigh the benefits, or is there no difference?*

Value	Label
1	Benefits outweigh risks
2	Risks outweigh benefits
3	No difference

vacrisk2**Available in:** All countries**Question:** *Are the health benefits of vaccinations much greater or slightly greater?**Display logic: Displayed if vacrisk = 1 (respondent said benefits outweigh risks).*

Value	Label
1	Much greater
2	Slightly greater

vacrisk3**Available in:** All countries**Question:** *Are the risks of vaccinations much greater or slightly greater?**Display logic: Displayed if vacrisk = 2 (respondent said risks outweigh benefits).*

Value	Label
1	Much greater
2	Slightly greater

covsci**Available in:** All countries**Question:** *In general, how important should science be for making government decisions about COVID-19?*

Value	Label
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1	Not at all important
2	A little important
3	Moderately important
4	Very important
5	Extremely important

covforce

Available in: All countries

Question: *Some people think vaccination against COVID-19 should be legally required. Others think individuals should be allowed to choose whether or not they get vaccinated. Which is closer to your opinion?*

Value	Label
1	Everyone should be vaccinated
2	The individual should decide

Some people think the government should penalize individuals who choose not to get vaccinated. Others oppose this. Would you support or oppose the following penalties on individuals who choose not to get vaccinated for COVID-19?

Scale: 1 = Strongly support, 2 = Support a little, 3 = Neither support nor oppose, 4 = Oppose a little, 5 = Strongly oppose. Prefer not to answer was offered but excluded from export.

Available in: All countries

Variable	Item
covpen_1	A financial penalty / fine
covpen_2	Lose job
covpen_3	One month prison sentence
covpen_4	Temporarily remove custody of their children

Note: The Brazil Public file includes additional COVID-related items not present in the cross-country aligned data. These include questions on COVID testing access, personal illness experience, loss of relatives, job loss, government response approval, views on pandemic restrictions, vaccine safety beliefs, alternative treatments, mask effectiveness, and lab-leak beliefs. See the Brazil companion codebook for details.

Degrowth

dg1

Available in: UK

Question: *Here are two statements people sometimes make when discussing the environment and economic growth.*

Value	Label
1	Protecting the environment should be given priority, even if it causes slower economic growth and some loss of jobs
2	Economic growth and creating jobs should be the top priority, even if the environment suffers to some extent

dg2**Available in:** UK

Question: *Some people say that to solve the climate crisis individuals need to reduce their personal consumption. That means, for example, using less electricity, limiting air travel, buying fewer clothes, and supermarkets stocking fewer imported goods (like fresh fruit and vegetables).*

Value	Label
1	Not at all
2	A little
3	Quite a bit
4	A great deal

dgns**Available in:** UK

Question: *Tackling climate change will mean sharing costs and burdens across the planet. Which countries should pay the most?*

Value	Label
1	All countries should contribute equally
2	Richer countries should pay more (e.g., USA, Germany, United Kingdom)
3	The countries that produce the most carbon emissions should pay more (e.g., India, China and Russia)

dgcov**Available in:** UK

Question: *Think about the restrictions and lifestyle changes that were implemented during the COVID-19 lockdowns (e.g., limited travel, fewer businesses open, reduced work hours, staying at home more). Would you be willing to accept similar types of restrictions if you knew it would greatly reduce climate change? If so, how many?*

Value	Label
1	None of the restrictions
2	A few of the restrictions
3	Quite a lot of restrictions

4	All of the restrictions
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em1**Available in:** UK

Question: *Protecting the environment might impact the jobs and living standards of workers in some industries (e.g., fuel, energy, agriculture, construction). As changes are made to protect the environment, how important is it to safeguard workers' jobs and conditions in these industries?*

Value	Label
1	Very important
2	Quite important
3	Not very important
4	Not at all important

em2**Available in:** UK

Question: *Here are three statements people sometimes make when discussing the relationship between jobs and the environment. Which of them comes closest to your own point of view?*

Value	Label
1	Protecting the environment should be given priority, even if it means some people lose their jobs
2	Creating jobs and protecting the environment should be given equal priority, even if progress towards environmental targets slows down
3	Creating jobs should be given priority, even if the environment suffers to some extent

Some people say that to solve the climate crisis individuals need to reduce their personal consumption. Would you be willing to do any of the following if you knew it would greatly reduce climate change?

Scale: 1 = Yes, 2 = No. Prefer not to answer was offered but excluded from export.

Available in: UK

Variable	Item
dg3_1	Buy fewer clothes
dg3_2	Buy less food
dg3_3	Eat less meat and dairy products
dg3_4	Pay more for locally sourced food rather than buying cheaper imports
dg3_5	Use less electricity and/or heating in your home
dg3_6	Travel less for holidays

dg3_7	Use public transport instead of owning a car
dg3_8	Pay higher taxes

Social Class

The social class variables in this survey are based on Erik Olin Wright's class analysis framework. Respondents are classified according to their position in relations of production, with employees subdivided by authority over other workers and possession of scarce skills or credentials. The questions follow a branching structure: all respondents who are currently employed (socecon = 1, 2, or 3) receive the class battery. All respondents, regardless of employment status, are asked about subjective class identification (class_self).

class

Available in: Croatia, Germany, Poland, UK, USA

Question: *Are you employed by someone else, are you self-employed, or do you work without pay in your own business?*

Display logic: *Displayed if socecon = 1, 2, or 3 (respondent is currently employed full-time, part-time, or self-employed).*

Value	Label
1	Employed by someone else
2	Self-employed
3	Work without pay

class_sect

Available in: Croatia, Germany, Poland, UK, USA

Question: *Do you work for a government or public institution, a private business or industry, or a nonprofit organization?*

Display logic: *Displayed if class = 1 (respondent is employed by someone else).*

Value	Label
1	Government or public institution
2	Private business or industry
3	Nonprofit

class_own

Available in: Croatia, Germany, Poland, UK, USA

Question: *Are you an owner or part owner of this business?*

Display logic: *Displayed if class_sect = 2 (private sector), class = 2 (self-employed), or class = 3 (works without pay).*

Value	Label
1	Yes

2	No
---	----

class_own2

Available in: Croatia, Germany, Poland, UK, USA

Question: Are you a partner at this firm or do you own stock?

Display logic: Displayed if class_own = 1 (respondent is an owner or part-owner).

Value	Label
1	Just own stock
2	Actual owner / partner

class_emp

Available in: All countries

Question: Are there any paid employees in this business? That is, nonfamily members who work for wages?

Display logic: Displayed if class = 2 (self-employed) or class = 3 (works without pay).

Value	Label
1	Yes
2	No

class_emp_no

Available in: All countries

Question: How many people are employed in this business?

Display logic: Displayed if class_own2 = 2 (actual owner/partner) or class_emp = 1 (business has paid employees).

Value	Label
1	No employees
2	1-20 employees
3	More than 20 employees

class_skill

Available in: All countries

Question: If your job were being advertised today, what is the minimum level of education or training that would be required for someone to be hired?

Display logic: Displayed if socecon = 1, 2, or 3 (respondent is currently employed).

Value	Label
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1	No qualifications required
2	High school education
3	50 hours or more of work specific training
4	University or college degree
5	Postgraduate qualification (e.g. teacher training qualification, masters, PhD, or any other qualification required after completing undergraduate degree)

class_skill2

Available in: UK, USA

Question: *Were you required to do training when you started your job? If so, how much?*

Display logic: Displayed if socecon = 1, 2, or 3 (respondent is currently employed).

Value	Label
1	No
2	Yes, 0-25 hours
3	Yes, 25-50 hours
4	Yes, 50 or more hours

class_sup

Available in: All countries

Question: *As an official part of your job, do you supervise the work of other employees or tell other employees what work to do?*

Display logic: Displayed if class = 1 (respondent is employed by someone else).

Value	Label
1	Yes
2	No

class_man

Available in: All countries

Question: *The next question is about policy-making at your workplace - that is, making decisions about things like products or services purchased, determining the total number of people employed, developing budgets, etc.*

Display logic: Displayed if class = 1 (respondent is employed by someone else).

Value	Label
1	Yes
2	No

Display logic: Displayed if class_sup = 1 (respondent supervises other employees).

As part of your job, are you directly responsible for any of the following?

Scale: 1 = Yes, 2 = No. Prefer not to answer was offered but excluded from export.

Available in: Croatia, Germany, Poland, UK, USA

Variable	Item
class_sup2_2	Giving input on pay raises or promotions for a subordinate
class_sup2_3	Giving input on decisions to fire or suspend a subordinate

class_self

Available in: All countries

Question: *People sometimes describe themselves as belonging to the working class, the middle class, or the upper or lower class. Which would you describe yourself as?*

Value	Label
1	Upper class
2	Middle class
3	Working class
4	Lower class

Display logic: Displayed if class_man = 1 (respondent participates in policy-making decisions).

As part of your work, do you participate or provide input on any of the following decisions?

Scale: 1 = Yes, 2 = No. Prefer not to answer was offered but excluded from export.

Available in: All countries

Variable	Item
class_man2_1	Increasing or decreasing the total number of people employed in the place where you work
class_man2_2	Decisions concerning the budget at the place where you work

Education: Country-Specific (Germany)

edu2

Available in: Germany

Question: *Was ist der höchste berufliche Ausbildungsabschluss, den Sie erreicht haben?*

Respondents who select "Other" are prompted to provide an open-text response, stored in edu2_11_TEXT (Germany).

United Kingdom

Companion Codebook

Language: English

Data Source: Qualtrics

Sample: 2,109

Question text and response labels are shown in the original language as administered to respondents.

United Kingdom

Survey Metadata

StartDate

EndDate

Duration..in.seconds.

consent

Question: *This survey is about organisations, COVID-19, politics, and civic engagement. Your participation will help us to better understand opinions about these issues. You are not required to answer any of the following questions and can decide at any point to withdraw from the survey. Your answers will be anonymous. We appreciate your time and thank you for giving thoughtful and honest answers to each of the questions in this important survey.*

Value	Label
1	I AGREE to participate in the survey
2	I DECLINE to participate

Demographics

gender

Question: *What is your gender?*

Respondents who select “Other” are prompted to provide an open-text response, stored in gender_4_TEXT.

Value	Label
1	Male
2	Female
3	Non-binary
4	Other

age

Question: *How old are you?*

Value	Label
1	18
2	19

3	20
...	<i>(value = age - 17)</i>
75	92
76	93
83	100
93	Prefer not to answer

Note: Coding follows the pattern $value = age - 17$ (e.g., 1 = 18 years old, 50 = 67 years old). The value 93 is reserved for “Prefer not to answer” and should be treated as missing.

edu

Question: What is the highest level of education you have completed?

Value	Label
1	Less than high school
2	High school
3	Vocational education
4	Some college
5	Bachelor's degree
6	Master's degree
7	PhD PhD or other postgraduate qualification

ethnicity

Question: What is your ethnicity? Select all that apply.

Respondents who select “Other” are prompted to provide an open-text response, stored in *ethnicity_2_TEXT*, *ethnicity_6_TEXT*, *ethnicity_7_TEXT*, *ethnicity_15_TEXT*.

Value	Label
1	White
2	Black
3	South Asian Indian, Pakistani etc.
4	East Asian Chinese, Japanese etc.
5	Arabic, Central Asian
6	Latino/Latina/Latinx
7	Other

live

Question: Where do you live?

Respondents who select “Other” are prompted to provide an open-text response, stored in `live_3_TEXT`, `live_4_TEXT`.

Value	Label
1	An urban area (e.g., a city or town)
2	A suburb
3	A rural area
4	Other

born

Question: *Were you born in the UK?*

Respondents who select “No (not born in country)” are prompted to provide an open-text response, stored in `born_2_TEXT`.

Value	Label
1	Yes
2	No

reg

Question: *Which region of the UK do you live in?*

Value	Label
1	Scotland
2	Wales
3	Northern Ireland
4	England (North East)
5	England (North West)
6	England (Midlands)
7	England (South East)
8	England (South West)

socecon

Question: *What best describes your current work situation?*

Value	Label
1	30 hours a week or more
2	Less than 30 hours a week
3	Self employed

4	Retired / pensioned
5	Homemaker not otherwise employed
6	Student
7	Unemployed
8	Disabled

relig_imp

Question: *How important is religion in your life?*

Value	Label
1	Not at all important
2–9	(...)
10	Very important

relig_dom

Question: *Do you belong to a religion or religious denomination?*

Value	Label
1	Yes
2	No

relig_dom2

Question: *Which religious denomination do you belong to?*

Respondents who select “Other” are prompted to provide an open-text response, stored in relig_dom2_7_TEXT, relig_dom2_8_TEXT, relig_dom2_11_TEXT.

Display logic: Displayed if relig_dom = 1 (respondent belongs to a religion or religious denomination).

Value	Label
1	Roman Catholic
2	Protestant
3	Orthodox (Russian, Greek, etc.)
4	Jewish
5	Muslim
6	Hindu
7	Buddhist
8	Other

house

Question: Which of the following best describes your housing situation?

Value	Label
1	I own my own house
2	I rent
3	I live with family or friends
4	I am currently unhoused

inc_alt

Question: Below is a list of incomes. We would like to know your *HOUSEHOLD INCOME*. In other words, before taxes, what is the combined income of all earners in your household from all sources, including wages, salaries, pensions or any other form of income.

Value	Label
1	A) Less than £9,999 per year
2	B) £10,000 to £14,999 per year
3	C) £15,000 to £19,999 per year
4	D) £20,000 to £24,999 per year
5	E) £25,000 to £29,999 per year
6	F) £30,000 to £39,999 per year
7	G) £40,000 to £49,999 per year
8	H) £50,000 to £59,999 per year
9	I) £60,000 to £99,999 per year
10	J) £100,000 to £149,999 per year
11	K) £150,000 or more per year

Populist Attitudes: People-Centrism

Do you agree or disagree with the following statements?

Scale: 1 = Strongly disagree, 2 = Disagree, 3 = Neither agree nor disagree, 4 = Agree, 5 = Strongly agree.
Prefer not to answer was offered but excluded from export.

Variable	Item
peoplec_pre_1	Politicians should always listen closely to the problems of the people.
peoplec_pre_2	Politicians don't have to spend time among ordinary people to do a good job.
peoplec_pre_3	The will of the people should be the highest principle in this country's politics.

Populist Attitudes: Anti-Elitism

Do you agree or disagree with the following statements?

Scale: 1 = Strongly disagree, 2 = Disagree, 3 = Neither agree nor disagree, 4 = Agree, 5 = Strongly agree.
Prefer not to answer was offered but excluded from export.

Variable	Item
antie_pre_1	The government is pretty much run by a few big interests looking out for themselves.
antie_pre_2	Government officials use their power to try to improve people's lives.
antie_pre_3	Quite a few of the people running the government are crooked.

Populist Attitudes: Manicheanism

Do you agree or disagree with the following statements?

Scale: 1 = Strongly disagree, 2 = Disagree, 3 = Neither agree nor disagree, 4 = Agree, 5 = Strongly agree.
Prefer not to answer was offered but excluded from export.

Variable	Item
manich_pre_1	You can tell if a person is good or bad if you know their politics.
manich_pre_2	The people I disagree with politically are not evil or bad people.
manich_pre_3	The people I disagree with politically are just misinformed.

Trust in Institutions (Feeling Thermometer)

How would you rate the following groups and organisations? Ratings between 50 degrees and 100 degrees mean that you feel favorable and warm toward the group or organisation. Ratings between 0 degrees and 50 degrees mean that you feel negatively about them. Rate the group at the 50-degree mark if you don't feel particularly warm or cold toward them. If you do not recognize a group or institution, click "prefer not to answer."

Scale: 0–100 feeling thermometer (0 = cold/unfavorable, 50 = neutral, 100 = warm/favorable). Prefer not to answer was offered but excluded from export.

Variable	Item
th_pre_1	Journalists
th_pre_4	Scientists
th_pre_5	University professors
th_pre_6	Civil servants
th_pre_7	Parliament
th_pre_8	The European Union (EU)
th_pre_9	Political parties
th_pre_10	Major companies

th_pre_11	Capitalists
th_pre_12	The police
th_pre_13	The military
th_pre_16	The Catholic Church
th_pre_17	The North Atlantic Treaty Organisation (NATO)
th_pre_18	The International Monetary Fund (IMF)

Nationalism

Some people say the following things are important to be truly British. Others say they are not important. How important do you think each of the following is?

Scale: 1 = Not at all important, 2 = Not important, 3 = Quite important, 4 = Very important. Prefer not to answer was offered but excluded from export.

Variable	Item
nat_pre_1	To have been born in the UK
nat_pre_2	To have British ancestry
nat_pre_3	To be able to speak English
nat_pre_4	To share British culture

Attitudes Towards Democracy

dem_pre

Question: *How important is it for you to live in a country that is governed democratically? On this scale where 1 means “not at all important” and 10 means “absolutely important,” what position would you choose?*

Value	Label
1	Not at all important
2–9	(...)
10	Absolutely important

Below are descriptions of various types of political systems. For each one, would you say it is a very good, fairly good, fairly bad, or very bad way of governing your country?

Scale: 1 = Very good, 2 = Fairly good, 3 = Fairly bad, 4 = Very bad. Prefer not to answer was offered but excluded from export.

Variable	Item
polsys_pre_1	Having a strong leader who does not have to bother with parliament and elections

polsys_pre_2	Having experts, not government, make decisions according to what they think is best for the country
polsys_pre_3	Having a democratic political system
polsys_pre_4	Having the army rule the country

Political Orientation and Ideology

ideol_self

Question: *In political matters, people talk of ‘the left’ and ‘the right’. How would you place your views on this scale generally speaking?*

Value	Label
1	The left
2–9	(...)
10	The right

ideol_respo

Question: *How would you place your views on this scale?*

Value	Label
1	Individuals should take more responsibility for providing for themselves
2–9	(...)
10	The state should take more responsibility to ensure that everyone is provided for

ideol_eq

Question: *How would you place your views on this scale?*

Value	Label
1	Private ownership of business and industry should be increased
2–9	(...)
10	There should be greater incentives for individual effort

ideol_own

Question: *How would you place your views on this scale?*

Value	Label
1	Private ownership of business and industry should be increased
2–9	(...)

10	Government ownership of business and industry should be increased
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brexit

Question: *How did you vote in the Brexit referendum in 2016?*

Value	Label
1	I voted to LEAVE the European Union (EU)
2	I voted to REMAIN in the European Union (EU)
3	I did not vote

Authoritarian Attitudes

How much do you agree or disagree with the following statements?

Scale: 1 = Strongly disagree, 2 = Disagree, 3 = Neither agree nor disagree, 4 = Agree, 5 = Strongly agree. Prefer not to answer was offered but excluded from export.

Variable	Item
al_1	Young people today don't have enough respect for traditional values
al_2	For some crimes, the death penalty is the most appropriate sentence
al_3	Schools should teach children to obey authority

Political Mobilization

Have you ever engaged in any of the following forms of political action? Please tell us if you have engaged in any of these, would engage in any of these, or would never engage in any of these.

Scale: 1 = Have done, 2 = Would do, 3 = Would never do. Prefer not to answer was offered but excluded from export.

Variable	Item
mobi_1	Have done
mobi_2	Join a boycott
mobi_3	Work with other people to deal with an issue facing your community
mobi_4	Attend a lawful demonstration

Political Interest and Voting

pol_i

Question: *How interested would you say you are in politics?*

Value	Label
1	Very interested
2	Somewhat interested
3	Not very interested
4	Not at all interested

pol_vote

Question: *If there were a national election tomorrow, for which party on this list would you vote? Respondents who select “Other” are prompted to provide an open-text response, stored in pol_vote_5_TEXT.*

Value	Label
1	The Conservative Party
2	The Labour Party
3	The Liberal Democrats
4	The Green Party
5	Reform UK
6	Plaid Cymru
7	The Scottish National Party
8	Other

Satisfaction and Alienation

sat

Question: *All things considered, how satisfied are you with your life as a whole these days?*

Value	Label
1	Dissatisfied
2–9	(...)
10	Satisfied

alien

Question: *Some people feel they have completely free choice and control over their lives, and other people feel that what they do has no real effect on what happens to them. Please use the scale to indicate how much freedom of choice and control you feel you have over the way your life turns out?*

Value	Label
1	None at all
2–9	(...)

10	A great deal of control
----	-------------------------

cap

Question: *To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statement? In my daily life I get very little chance to show how capable I am.*

Value	Label
1	Strongly disagree
2	Disagree
3	Neither agree nor disagree
4	Agree
5	Strongly agree

Neighborhood Conditions

How frequently do the following things occur in your neighbourhood?

Scale: 1 = Extremely often, 2 = Often, 3 = Sometimes, 4 = Rarely, 5 = Never. Prefer not to answer was offered but excluded from export.

Variable	Item
hood_1	Robberies
hood_2	Alcohol consumption in the streets
hood_3	Police interfere with people's private life

Economic Perceptions

econ

Question: *What do you think about the state of the economy these days in the United Kingdom? Would you say the state of the economy is good, neither good nor bad, or bad?*

Value	Label
1	Good
2	Neither good nor bad
3	Bad

econg

Question: *How good would you say the state of the economy is?*
Display logic: Displayed if econ = 1 (respondent said economy is good).

Value	Label
1	Somewhat good
2	Very good
3	Extremely good

econb

Question: *How bad do you think the state of the economy is?*

Display logic: Displayed if econ = 3 (respondent said economy is bad).

Value	Label
1	Somewhat bad
2	Very bad
3	Extremely bad

fsit

Question: *So far as you and your family are concerned, how worried are you about your current financial situation?*

Value	Label
1	Not at all
2	A little
3	Moderately
4	Very
5	Extremely

Sexual Harassment Attitudes

harass

Question: *Do you think attention to sexual harassment has gone too far, has not gone far enough, or has been about right?*

Value	Label
1	Has gone too far
2	Has been about right
3	Has not gone far enough

harass2

Question: *Do you think attention to sexual harassment has gone a little too far, or much too far?*

Display logic: Displayed if harass = 1 (respondent said attention has gone too far).

Value	Label
1	Has gone a little too far
2	Has gone much too far

harass3

Question: *Do you think attention to sexual harassment has not gone quite far enough, or not nearly far enough?*

Display logic: Displayed if harass = 3 (respondent said attention has not gone far enough).

Value	Label
1	Has not gone quite far enough
2	Has not gone nearly far enough

Immigration and Ethnic Relations

methnic

Question: *Does increasing the number of people of different races and ethnic groups in the UK make this country a better place to live, a worse place to live, or does it make no difference?*

Value	Label
1	Better
2	Makes no difference
3	Worse

methnic2

Question: *Does increasing the number of people of different races and ethnic groups make the UK a little better place to live, or a lot better place to live?*

Display logic: Displayed if methnic = 1 (respondent said diversity makes country better).

Value	Label
1	A little better
2	A lot better

methnic3

Question: *Does increasing the number of people of different races and ethnic groups make the UK a little worse place to live, or a lot worse place to live?*

Display logic: Displayed if methnic = 3 (respondent said diversity makes country worse).

Value	Label
-------	-------

1	A little worse
2	A lot worse

COVID-19 and Vaccination

cov

Question: *Were you infected with COVID-19 between 2020 and 2022?*

Value	Label
1	Yes
2	No

vac

Question: *Have you been vaccinated against COVID-19?*

Value	Label
1	Yes
2	No

die

Question: *Did any of your family members die as a direct result of COVID-19 between 2020 and 2022?*

Value	Label
1	Yes
2	No

die2

Question: *How many of your family members died as a direct result of COVID-19 between 2020 and 2022?*

Display logic: Displayed if die = 1 (respondent said yes, a family member died of COVID).

Value	Label
1	1
2	2
3	3
4	4
5	5 or more

vacrisk

Question: *Do the health benefits of vaccinations generally outweigh the risks, do the risks outweigh the benefits, or is there no difference?*

Value	Label
1	Benefits outweigh risks
2	Risks outweigh benefits
3	No difference

vacrisk2

Question: *Are the health benefits of vaccinations much greater or slightly greater?*

Display logic: Displayed if vacrisk = 1 (respondent said benefits outweigh risks).

Value	Label
1	Much greater
2	Slightly greater

vacrisk3

Question: *Are the risks of vaccinations much greater or slightly greater?*

Display logic: Displayed if vacrisk = 2 (respondent said risks outweigh benefits).

Value	Label
1	Much greater
2	Slightly greater

covsci

Question: *In general, how important should science be for making government decisions about COVID-19?*

Value	Label
1	Not at all important
2	A little important
3	Moderately important
4	Very important
5	Extremely important

covforce

Question: *Some people think vaccination against COVID-19 should be legally required. Others think individuals should be allowed to choose whether or not they get vaccinated. Which is closer to your opinion?*

Value	Label
1	Everyone should be vaccinated
2	The individual should decide

Some people think the government should penalise individuals who choose not to get vaccinated against COVID-19. Others oppose this. Would you support or oppose the following penalties on individuals who choose not to get vaccinated?

Scale: 1 = Strongly Support, 2 = Support a little, 3 = Neither support nor oppose, 4 = Oppose a little, 5 = Strongly Oppose. Prefer not to answer was offered but excluded from export.

Variable	Item
covpen_1	A financial penalty / fine
covpen_2	One month prison sentence
covpen_3	Temporarily remove custody of their children
covpen_4	Lose job

Degrowth

dg1

Question: *Here are two statements people sometimes make when discussing the environment and economic growth.*

Value	Label
1	Protecting the environment should be given priority, even if it causes slower economic growth and some loss of jobs
2	Economic growth and creating jobs should be the top priority, even if the environment suffers to some extent

dg2

Question: *Some people say that to solve the climate crisis individuals need to reduce their personal consumption. That means, for example, using less electricity, limiting air travel, buying fewer clothes, and supermarkets stocking fewer imported goods (like fresh fruit and vegetables).*

Value	Label
1	Not at all
2	A little
3	Quite a bit

4	A great deal
---	--------------

dgns

Question: *Tackling climate change will mean sharing costs and burdens across the planet. Which countries should pay the most?*

Value	Label
1	All countries should contribute equally
2	Richer countries should pay more (e.g., USA, Germany, United Kingdom)
3	The countries that produce the most carbon emissions should pay more (e.g., India, China and Russia)

dgcov

Question: *Think about the restrictions and lifestyle changes that were implemented during the COVID-19 lockdowns (e.g., limited travel, fewer businesses open, reduced work hours, staying at home more). Would you be willing to accept similar types of restrictions if you knew it would greatly reduce climate change? If so, how many?*

Value	Label
1	None of the restrictions
2	A few of the restrictions
3	Quite a lot of restrictions
4	All of the restrictions

em1

Question: *Protecting the environment might impact the jobs and living standards of workers in some industries (e.g., fuel, energy, agriculture, construction). As changes are made to protect the environment, how important is it to safeguard workers' jobs and conditions in these industries?*

Value	Label
1	Very important
2	Quite important
3	Not very important
4	Not at all important

em2

Question: *Here are three statements people sometimes make when discussing the relationship between jobs and the environment. Which of them comes closest to your own point of view?*

Value	Label
1	Protecting the environment should be given priority, even if it means some people lose their jobs
2	Creating jobs and protecting the environment should be given equal priority, even if progress towards environmental targets slows down
3	Creating jobs should be given priority, even if the environment suffers to some extent

Some people say that to solve the climate crisis individuals need to reduce their personal consumption. Would you be willing to do any of the following if you knew it would greatly reduce climate change?

Scale: 1 = Yes, 2 = No. Prefer not to answer was offered but excluded from export.

Variable	Item
dg3_1	Yes
dg3_2	Buy less food
dg3_3	Eat less meat and dairy products
dg3_4	Pay more for locally sourced food rather than buying cheaper imports
dg3_5	Use less electricity and/or heating in your home
dg3_6	Travel less for holidays
dg3_7	Use public transport instead of owning a car
dg3_8	Pay higher taxes

Social Class

The social class variables in this survey are based on Erik Olin Wright's class analysis framework. Respondents are classified according to their position in relations of production, with employees subdivided by authority over other workers and possession of scarce skills or credentials. The questions follow a branching structure: all respondents who are currently employed (socecon = 1, 2, or 3) receive the class battery. All respondents, regardless of employment status, are asked about subjective class identification (class_self).

class

Question: *Are you employed by someone else, are you self-employed, or do you work without pay in your own business?*

Display logic: Displayed if socecon = 1, 2, or 3 (respondent is currently employed full-time, part-time, or self-employed).

Value	Label
1	Employed by someone else
2	Self-employed
3	Work without pay

class_sect

Question: *Do you work for a government or public institution, a private business or industry, or a nonprofit organization?*

Display logic: Displayed if class = 1 (respondent is employed by someone else).

Value	Label
1	Government or public institution
2	Private business or industry
3	Nonprofit / third sector

class_own

Question: *Are you an owner or part owner of this business?*

Display logic: Displayed if class_sect = 2 (private sector), class = 2 (self-employed), or class = 3 (works without pay).

Value	Label
1	Yes
2	No

class_own2

Question: *Are you a partner at this firm or do you own stock?*

Display logic: Displayed if class_own = 1 (respondent is an owner or part-owner).

Value	Label
1	Just own stock
2	Actual owner / partner

class_emp

Question: *Are there any paid employees in this business? That is, nonfamily members who work for wages?*

Display logic: Displayed if class = 2 (self-employed) or class = 3 (works without pay).

Value	Label
1	Yes
2	No

class_emp_no

Question: *How many people are employed in this business?*

Display logic: Displayed if class_own2 = 2 (actual owner/partner) or class_emp = 1 (business has paid employees).

Value	Label
1	No employees
2	1-20 employees
3	More than 20 employees

class_skill

Question: *If your job were being advertised today, what is the minimum level of education or training that would be required for someone to be hired?*

Display logic: Displayed if socecon = 1, 2, or 3 (respondent is currently employed).

Value	Label
1	No qualifications required
2	High school education
3	50 hours or more of work specific training
4	University or college degree
5	Postgraduate qualification (e.g., teacher training, masters, PhD, or any other qualification required after completing undergraduate degree)

class_skill2

Question: *Were you required to do training when you started your job? If so, how much?*

Display logic: Displayed if socecon = 1, 2, or 3 (respondent is currently employed).

Value	Label
1	No
2	Yes, 0-25 hours
3	Yes, 25-50 hours
4	Yes, 50 or more hours

class_sup

Question: *As an official part of your job, do you supervise the work of other employees or tell other employees what work to do?*

Display logic: Displayed if class = 1 (respondent is employed by someone else).

Value	Label
1	Yes
2	No

class_man

Question: *The next question is about policy-making at your workplace - that is, making decisions about things like products or services purchased, determining the total number of people employed, developing budgets, etc.*

Display logic: Displayed if class = 1 (respondent is employed by someone else).

Value	Label
1	Yes
2	No

Display logic: Displayed if class_sup = 1 (respondent supervises other employees).

As part of your job, are you directly responsible for any of the following?

Scale: 1 = Yes, 2 = No. Prefer not to answer was offered but excluded from export.

Variable	Item
class_sup2_2	Giving input on pay rises or promotions for a subordinate
class_sup2_3	Giving input on decisions to fire or suspend a subordinate

class_self

Question: *People sometimes describe themselves as belonging to the working class, the middle class, or the upper or lower class. Which would you describe yourself as?*

Value	Label
1	Upper class
2	Middle class
3	Working class
4	Lower class

Display logic: Displayed if class_man = 1 (respondent participates in policy-making decisions).

As part of your work, do you participate or provide input on any of the following decisions?

Scale: 1 = Yes, 2 = No. Prefer not to answer was offered but excluded from export.

Variable	Item
class_man2_1	Increasing or decreasing the total number of people employed in the place where you work
class_man2_2	Decisions concerning the budget at the place where you work

Brazil

Companion Codebook

Language: Portuguese

Data Source: Netquest

Sample: 2,047

Question text and response labels are shown in the original language as administered to respondents.

Brazil

Survey Metadata

Duration..in.seconds.

Demographics

gender

Question: Qual o seu sexo?

Respondents who select “Other” are prompted to provide an open-text response, stored in `gender_4_TEXT`.

Value	Label
1	Masculino
2	Feminino
3	Não-binário
4	Outro

age

Question: Qual a sua idade?

Value	Label
1	18
2	19
3	20
...	(value = age - 17)
75	92
76	93
83	100
93	Prefiro não responder

Note: Coding follows the pattern $value = age - 17$ (e.g., 1 = 18 years old, 50 = 67 years old). The value 93 is reserved for “Prefiro não responder” and should be treated as missing.

edu

Question: Qual foi o nível de escolaridade mais elevado que completou?

Value	Label
1	Nenhum/ensino básico ou primário incompleto
9	Ensino Básico completo (até a 5a série)

10	Ensino Fundamental incompleto
11	Ensino Fundamental completo
12	Ensino médio incompleto
13	Ensino médio completo
14	Ensino técnico incompleto
15	Ensino técnico completo
16	Superior incompleto
17	Superior completo
18	Mestrado
19	Doutorado

ethnicity

Question: Qual a sua cor ou raça?

Respondents who select “Other” are prompted to provide an open-text response, stored in *ethnicity_2_TEXT*, *ethnicity_6_TEXT*, *ethnicity_7_TEXT*, *ethnicity_15_TEXT*.

Value	Label
1	Branca
2	Preta
3	Parda
4	Amarela
5	Indígena
7	Outro

live

Question: Em que área você vive?

Respondents who select “Other” are prompted to provide an open-text response, stored in *live_3_TEXT*, *live_4_TEXT*.

Value	Label
1	Numa área urbana (uma cidade ou vilarejo)
2	Uma área rural
3	Outro

socecon

Question: Tem atualmente um trabalho ou uma ocupação remunerada? Qual das seguintes situações se aplica à sua condição perante o trabalho?

Value	Label
1	Tenho um trabalho ou uma ocupação remunerada
2	Não trabalho: Sou reformado/aposentado/pensionista
3	Faço trabalho doméstico/dona de casa
4	Sou apenas estudante
5	Estudo e tenho um trabalho ou ocupação remunerada
6	Não trabalho, não estudo e não estou procurando emprego
7	Estou desempregado/a, procurando ativamente um emprego/ocupação

relig_dom

Question: *Pertence a alguma religião?*

Value	Label
1	Sim
2	Não

relig_dom2

Question: *A qual religião você pertence?*

Respondents who select “Other” are prompted to provide an open-text response, stored in relig_dom2_7_TEXT, relig_dom2_8_TEXT, relig_dom2_11_TEXT.

Display logic: Displayed if relig_dom = 1 (respondent belongs to a religion or religious denomination).

Value	Label
1	Católica
2	Protestante (Luterana, Presbiteriana, Metodista, Batista, Adventista, Anglicana)
3	Evangélica/pentecostal/neopentecostal
4	Outra cristã
5	Espírita
6	Religião afro-brasileira
7	Judaica
8	Outra não-cristã
10	Islâmica / Muçulmana

house

Question: *Qual das alternativas a seguir melhor descreve sua situação de moradia?*

Value	Label
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1	Sou o/a proprietário/a da casa
2	A casa onde moro é alugada
3	Moro com a família ou amigos
4	A casa é cedida por terceiros

inc_alt

Question: *Se somar o rendimento de todas as fontes, de todas as pessoas com rendimento em sua família, qual faixa de renda melhor descreve o rendimento familiar total, retirando os descontos em impostos ou outros tipos de deduções (rendimento mensal).*

Value	Label
1	A) 1,00 a 500,00 reais
2	B) 501,00 a 1.000,00
3	C) 1.001,00 a 2.000,00
4	D) 2.001,00 a 3.000,00
5	E) 3.001,00 a 5.000,00
6	F) 5.001,00 a 10.000,00
7	G) 10.001,00 a 20.000,00
8	H) 20.001,00 a 100.000
9	I) 100.001 reais ou mais

Populist Attitudes: People-Centrism

Diga, por favor, em que medida concorda ou discorda com cada uma das seguintes afirmações.

Scale: 1 = Discordo totalmente, 2 = Discordo, 3 = Nem concordo nem discordo, 4 = Concordo, 5 = Concordo totalmente. Prefer not to answer was offered but excluded from export.

Variable	Item
peoplec_pre_1	Políticos deveriam sempre ouvir com cuidado os problemas do povo
peoplec_pre_2	Os políticos não precisam passar tempo com pessoas comuns para fazerem um bom trabalho
peoplec_pre_3	A vontade do povo deveria ser o princípio mais alto da política neste país

Populist Attitudes: Anti-Elitism

Diga, por favor, em que medida concorda ou discorda com cada uma das seguintes afirmações.

Scale: 1 = Discordo totalmente, 2 = Discordo, 3 = Nem concordo nem discordo, 4 = Concordo, 5 = Concordo totalmente. Prefer not to answer was offered but excluded from export.

Variable	Item
antie_pre_1	O governo é dirigido por alguns poucos grandes interesses que só se importam consigo mesmos.
antie_pre_2	Os servidores públicos usam seu poder para tentar melhorar a vida das pessoas.
antie_pre_3	Muitas pessoas no governo são desonestas.

Populist Attitudes: Manicheanism

Diga, por favor, em que medida concorda ou discorda com cada uma das seguintes afirmações.

Scale: 1 = Discordo totalmente, 2 = Discordo, 3 = Nem concordo nem discordo, 4 = Concordo, 5 = Concordo totalmente. Prefer not to answer was offered but excluded from export.

Variable	Item
manich_pre_1	Dá para saber se uma pessoa é boa ou má se você sabe as opiniões dela sobre política.
manich_pre_2	As pessoas de quem eu discordo em política não são más.
manich_pre_3	As pessoas de quem eu discordo em política são apenas mal informadas.

Trust in Institutions (Feeling Thermometer)

Por favor, avalie cada grupo ou organização usando algo que chamamos de “termômetro de sentimento”. Avaliações entre 50 graus e 100 graus significam que você se sente favorável e positivo em relação ao grupo. Avaliações entre 0 graus e 50 graus significam que você tem uma opinião negativa em relação a esse grupo.

Scale: 0–100 feeling thermometer (0 = cold/unfavorable, 50 = neutral, 100 = warm/favorable). Prefer not to answer was offered but excluded from export.

Variable	Item
th_pre_1	Os Jornalistas e a imprensa
th_pre_4	Os Cientistas
th_pre_5	Professores universitários
th_pre_6	Funcionários públicos
th_pre_7	O Congresso Nacional
th_pre_9	Os Partidos políticos
th_pre_10	As Grandes empresas multinacionais
th_pre_11	Os Capitalistas
th_pre_12	A polícia
th_pre_13	Os militares
th_pre_17	As igrejas evangélicas

th_pre_18	As Organizações Não Governamentais (ONGs)
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Nationalism

Há quem diga que para se ser verdadeiramente brasileiro é importante possuir certas características. Também há quem, pelo contrário, não as considere importantes.

Scale: 1 = Muito importante, 2 = Bastante importante, 3 = Pouco importante, 4 = Nada importante. Prefer not to answer was offered but excluded from export.

Variable	Item
nat_pre_1	Ter nascido no Brasil
nat_pre_2	Ter antepassados brasileiros
nat_pre_3	Saber falar português
nat_pre_4	Compartilhar a cultura brasileira

Attitudes Towards Democracy

dem_pre

Question: *Em que medida é importante para você viver num país governado democraticamente? Escolha a sua resposta nesta escala em que 1 significa 'nada importante' e 10 significa 'Extremamente importante'*

Value	Label
1	Nada importante
2–9	(...)
10	Extremamente importante

Diga como avalia cada uma das seguintes formas de governo para o Brasil

Scale: 1 = muito boa, 2 = boa, 3 = má, 4 = muito má. Prefer not to answer was offered but excluded from export.

Variable	Item
polsys_pre_1	Ter um líder forte que não tenha que se preocupar nem com o Congresso nem com as eleições
polsys_pre_2	Serem os especialistas e não os governantes a tomar as decisões de acordo com o que consideram ser melhor para o país
polsys_pre_3	Ter um sistema político democrático
polsys_pre_4	Serem as Forças Armadas a governar o país

Political Orientation and Ideology

ideol_self

Question: *Em política as pessoas falam ‘da esquerda’ e ‘da direita’. Como você se situaria, quanto às suas posições políticas, nesta escala?*

Value	Label
1	A esquerda
2–9	(...)
10	A direita

ideol_respo

Question: *Para cada par de opiniões opostas, em que ponto da escala situa a sua opinião pessoal?*

Value	Label
1	Individuals should take more responsibility for providing for themselves
2–9	(...)
10	The state should take more responsibility to ensure that everyone is provided for

ideol_eq

Question: *Para cada par de opiniões opostas, em que ponto da escala situa a sua opinião pessoal?*

Value	Label
1	Incomes should be made more equal
2–9	(...)
10	There should be greater incentives for individual effort

ideol_own

Question: *Para cada par de opiniões opostas, em que ponto da escala situa a sua opinião pessoal?*

Value	Label
1	Private ownership of business and industry should be increased
2–9	(...)
10	Government ownership of business and industry should be increased

Authoritarian Attitudes

O quanto você concorda ou discorda das seguintes afirmações?

Scale: 1 = Discordo totalmente, 2 = Discordo, 3 = Nem concordo nem discordo, 4 = Concordo, 5 = Concordo totalmente. Prefer not to answer was offered but excluded from export.

Variable	Item
al_1	Os jovens de hoje não respeitam suficientemente os valores tradicionais
al_2	Para alguns crimes, a pena de morte é a pena mais adequada
al_3	As escolas devem ensinar as crianças a obedecer à autoridade

Political Mobilization

Abaixo estão diferentes formas de ação política que as pessoas podem realizar. Por favor, diga-nos se você fez alguma dessas coisas, se faria ou nunca, em nenhuma circunstância, faria.

Scale: 1 = Sim, já fez, 2 = Não fez, mas admite fazer, 3 = Não fez e não admite fazer. Prefer not to answer was offered but excluded from export.

Variable	Item
mobi_1	Assinar uma petição ou um abaixo-assinado online
mobi_2	Participar em boicotes
mobi_3	Trabalhar com outras pessoas para resolver problemas em sua comunidade/bairro
mobi_4	Participar em manifestações legais

Political Interest and Voting

pol_i

Question: Qual o seu interesse pela política? xMuito interesse (1)

Value	Label
1	PT
2	PL
3	PSB
4	PSDB
5	Outro partido
7	MDB
8	Republicanos
9	União Brasil
10	Cidadania
11	PDT
12	PSD
13	PP

pol_vote

Question: *Se amanhã houvesse eleições nacionais, em qual partido desta lista você votaria? xPT (1)*
Respondents who select “Other” are prompted to provide an open-text response, stored in pol_vote_5_TEXT.

Value	Label
1	PT
2	PL
3	PSB
4	PSDB
5	Outro partido
7	MDB
8	Republicanos
9	União Brasil
10	Cidadania
11	PDT
12	PSD
13	PP

Satisfaction and Alienation**sat**

Question: *Considerando todos os aspectos da sua vida, numa escala de 1 a 10, na qual 1 quer dizer muito insatisfeito, e 10 muito satisfeito, qual o grau de satisfação que sente atualmente?*

Value	Label
1	Muito insatisfeito
2–9	(...)
10	Muito Satisfeito

alien

Question: *Algumas pessoas sentem que têm total liberdade de escolha e capacidade de controle sobre as suas vidas, outras sentem que as suas ações não têm qualquer efeito sobre aquilo que lhes acontece. Utilizando a seguinte escala, diga, por favor, qual o grau de liberdade de escolha e capacidade de controle que sente ter sobre aquilo que acontece em sua vida.*

Value	Label
1	Nenhuma liberdade
2–9	(...)
10	Muita liberdade

cap

Question: *Até que ponto você concorda ou discorda de cada uma das afirmações a seguir? Na minha vida diária tenho muito poucas chances de mostrar o quanto sou capaz. xDiscordo totalmente (1)*

Value	Label
1	Discordo totalmente
2	Discordo
3	Nem concordo nem discordo
4	Concordo
5	Concordo totalmente

Neighborhood Conditions

Com que frequência ocorrem as seguintes coisas na sua vizinhança?

Scale: 1 = Extremamente frequentemente, 2 = Frequentemente, 3 = Às vezes, 4 = Raramente, 5 = Nunca.
Prefer not to answer was offered but excluded from export.

Variable	Item
hood_1	Roubos
hood_2	Consumo de álcool nas ruas
hood_3	A polícia interferir na vida privada das pessoas

Economic Perceptions**econ**

Question: *O que você acha da situação atual da economia no Brasil? Você diria que o estado da economia é bom, nem bom nem ruim, ou ruim? xBom (1)*

Value	Label
1	Bom
2	Nem bom nem ruim
3	Ruim

econg

Question: *Quão bom você diria que é o estado da economia?*

Display logic: Displayed if econ = 1 (respondent said economy is good).

Value	Label
1	Um pouco bom

2	Muito bom
3	Extremamente bom

econb

Question: *Quão ruim você diria que é o estado da economia?*

Display logic: Displayed if econ = 3 (respondent said economy is bad).

Value	Label
1	Um pouco ruim
2	Muito ruim
3	Extremamente ruim

fsit

Question: *No que diz respeito a você e sua família, quão preocupado você está com sua situação financeira atual?*

Value	Label
1	Nem um pouco preocupado
2	Um pouco
3	Moderadamente
4	Muito
5	Extremamente preocupado

Sexual Harassment Attitudes**harass**

Question: *Você acha que a atenção que se dá ao assédio sexual hoje em dia foi longe demais, não foi longe o suficiente ou está de bom tamanho?*

Value	Label
1	Foi longe demais
2	Está de bom tamanho
3	Não foi longe o suficiente

harass2

Question: *Você acha que a atenção ao assédio sexual passou um pouco da conta, ou passou muito da conta?*

Display logic: Displayed if harass = 1 (respondent said attention has gone too far).

Value	Label
1	Passou muito da conta
2	Passou um pouco da conta

harass3

Question: *Você acha que a atenção ao assédio sexual está um pouco aquém do que deveria, ou muito aquém do que deveria?*

Display logic: Displayed if harass = 3 (respondent said attention has not gone far enough).

Value	Label
1	Um pouco aquém do que deveria

Immigration and Ethnic Relations

methnic

Question: *O aumento do número de pessoas de diferentes raças e grupos étnicos no Brasil faz deste país um lugar melhor para se viver, um lugar pior para se viver, ou não faz diferença?*

Value	Label
1	Melhor
2	Não faz diferença
3	Pior

methnic2

Question: *O aumento do número de pessoas de diferentes raças e grupos étnicos torna o Brasil um lugar um pouco melhor para se viver, ou um lugar muito melhor para se viver?*

Display logic: Displayed if methnic = 1 (respondent said diversity makes country better).

Value	Label
1	Um pouco melhor

methnic3

Question: *O aumento do número de pessoas de diferentes raças e grupos étnicos torna o Brasil um lugar um pouco pior para se viver, ou um lugar muito pior para se viver?*

Display logic: Displayed if methnic = 3 (respondent said diversity makes country worse).

Value	Label
1	Um pouco pior
2	Muito pior

COVID-19 and Vaccination

cov

Question: *Were you infected with COVID-19 between 2020 and 2022?*

Value	Label
1	Sim
2	Não

vac

Question: *Have you been vaccinated against COVID-19?*

Value	Label
1	Sim
2	Não

die

Question: *Did any of your family members die as a direct result of COVID-19 between 2020 and 2022?*

Value	Label
1	Sim
2	Não

vacrisk

Question: *Na sua opinião, os benefícios das vacinas geralmente superam os riscos para a saúde, os riscos superam os benefícios ou não há diferença?*

Value	Label
1	Os benefícios superam os riscos
2	Os riscos superam os benefícios
3	Sem diferença

vacrisk2

Question: *Os benefícios das vacinas para a saúde são muito maiores ou ligeiramente maiores? Display logic: Displayed if vacrisk = 1 (respondent said benefits outweigh risks).*

Value	Label
1	Much greater

2	Slightly greater
---	------------------

vacrisk3

Question: *Os riscos das vacinações são muito maiores ou ligeiramente maiores?*

Display logic: Displayed if vacrisk = 2 (respondent said risks outweigh benefits).

Value	Label
1	Muito maiores
2	Ligeiramente maiores

covsci

Question: *Em geral, qual deveria ser a importância da ciência na tomada de decisões governamentais sobre a COVID-19?*

Value	Label
1	Nada importante
2	Um pouco importante
3	Moderadamente importante
4	Muito importante

covforce

Question: *Algumas pessoas acham que a vacinação contra a covid deveria ser legalmente exigida. Outros acham que os indivíduos deveriam poder escolher se serão ou não vacinados. O que está mais próximo da sua opinião? xTodos deveriam ser vacinados (1)*

Value	Label
1	Todos deveriam ser vacinados
2	O indivíduo deve decidir

Algumas pessoas acham que o governo deveria penalizar os indivíduos que optam por não se vacinar. Outros se opõem a isso. Você apoiaria ou se oporia às seguintes penalidades para indivíduos que optam por não ser vacinados?

Scale: 1 = Apoiaria fortemente, 2 = Apoiaria um pouco, 3 = Nem apoiaria nem se oporia, 4 = Se oporia um pouco, 5 = Se oporia fortemente. Prefer not to answer was offered but excluded from export.

Variable	Item
covpen_1	Uma punição financeira/multa
covpen_2	Pena de prisão de um mês

covpen_3	Retirar temporariamente a custódia dos filhos
covpen_4	Perder o emprego

Social Class

The social class variables in this survey are based on Erik Olin Wright's class analysis framework. Respondents are classified according to their position in relations of production, with employees subdivided by authority over other workers and possession of scarce skills or credentials. The questions follow a branching structure: all respondents who are currently employed (socecon = 1, 2, or 3) receive the class battery. All respondents, regardless of employment status, are asked about subjective class identification (class_self).

class_emp

Question: *Há algum funcionário remunerado neste negócio? Ou seja, membros não familiares que trabalham por salário?*

Display logic: Displayed if class = 2 (self-employed) or class = 3 (works without pay).

Value	Label
1	Nenhum
2	1 empregado
3	2 a 5 empregados
4	6 a 10 empregados
5	10 a 20 empregados

class_emp_no

Question: *Quantos empregados tem?*

Display logic: Displayed if class_own2 = 2 (actual owner/partner) or class_emp = 1 (business has paid employees).

Value	Label
1	Nenhum
2	1 empregado
3	2 a 5 empregados
4	6 a 10 empregados
5	10 a 20 empregados

class_skill

Question: *Se o seu trabalho estivesse sendo anunciado, qual é o nível mínimo de escolaridade ou treinamento exigido para alguém fazer o seu trabalho?*

Display logic: Displayed if socecon = 1, 2, or 3 (respondent is currently employed).

Value	Label
-------	-------

1	Nenhuma qualificação necessária
2	Ensino médio
3	Menos de 50 horas de treinamento específico para o trabalho
4	50 horas ou mais de treinamento específico para o trabalho
5	Diploma universitário
6	Qualificação de pós-graduação (por exemplo, mestrado, doutorado ou qualquer outra qualificação exigida após a conclusão da graduação)

class_sup

Question: *Tem alguma responsabilidade de supervisão do trabalho de outras pessoas?*

Display logic: Displayed if class = 1 (respondent is employed by someone else).

Value	Label
1	Sim
2	Não

class_man

Question: *A próxima pergunta é sobre a elaboração de políticas no seu local de trabalho; isto é, tomar decisões sobre coisas como produtos ou serviços entregues, número total de pessoas empregadas, orçamentos, etc. Você participa da tomada desses tipos de decisões ou fornece conselhos sobre elas?*

Display logic: Displayed if class = 1 (respondent is employed by someone else).

Value	Label
1	Sim
2	Não

class_self

Question: *As pessoas às vezes se descrevem como pertencentes à classe trabalhadora, à classe média ou à classe alta ou baixa. Como você se descreveria?*

Value	Label
1	Classe alta
2	Classe média
3	Classe trabalhadora
4	Classe baixa

Display logic: Displayed if class_man = 1 (respondent participates in policy-making decisions).

Como parte do seu trabalho, você participa de algum dos seguintes tipos de tomada de decisão? Isso inclui fornecer conselhos sobre eles.

Scale: 1 = Yes, 2 = No. Prefer not to answer was offered but excluded from export.

Variable	Item
class_man2_1	Decisões de aumentar ou diminuir o número total de pessoas empregadas no local onde você trabalha?
class_man2_2	Decisões relativas ao orçamento no local onde trabalha?

Croatia

Companion Codebook

Language: Croatian

Data Source: Qualtrics

Sample: 1,600

Question text and response labels are shown in the original language as administered to respondents.

Croatia

Survey Metadata

StartDate

EndDate

Duration..in.seconds.

consent

Question: *Ovo istraživanje ispituje vaše mišljenje o djelovanju institucija, koronavirusu, politici i građanskom sudjelovanju u društveno-političkim procesima. Vaše sudjelovanje u ovoj anketi važno nam je kako bismo bolje razumjeli stavove javnosti spram ovih pitanja. Ipak, ne morate odgovoriti na sva pitanja i možete se u bilo kojem trenutku odlučiti povući iz istraživanja. Vaši odgovori će biti anonimni. Cijenimo vaše vrijeme i zahvaljujemo vam što dajete promišljene i iskrene odgovore na svako od pitan...*

Value	Label
1	SLAŽEM SE sudjelovati u anketi
2	ODBIJAM sudjelovanje

Demographics

gender

Question: *Kako identificirate vaš rod?*

Respondents who select "Other" are prompted to provide an open-text response, stored in gender_4_TEXT.

Value	Label
1	Muško
2	Žensko
3	Ne-binarno
4	Ostalo

age

Question: *Koliko imate godina?*

Value	Label
1	18

2	19
3	20
...	(value = age - 17)
75	92
76	93
83	100
93	Ne želim odgovoriti

Note: Coding follows the pattern value = age - 17 (e.g., 1 = 18 years old, 50 = 67 years old). The value 93 is reserved for “Ne želim odgovoriti” and should be treated as missing.

edu

Question: *Koja je najviša razina obrazovanja koju ste završili?*

Value	Label
1	Niže od srednje škole
2	Srednja škola
3	Nezavršen sveučilišni program
4	Sveučilišni prvi stupanj ili stručni studij
5	Magisterij
6	Doktorat

ethnicity

Question: *Koja je vaša etnička pripadnost? Označite sve što je primjenjivo.*

Respondents who select “Other” are prompted to provide an open-text response, stored in *ethnicity_2_TEXT*, *ethnicity_6_TEXT*, *ethnicity_7_TEXT*, *ethnicity_15_TEXT*.

Value	Label
1	Hrvatska
2	Ostalo

race

Question: *Koje ste rase? Označite sve što je primjenjivo.*

Respondents who select “Other” are prompted to provide an open-text response, stored in *race_3_TEXT*.

Value	Label
1	Bijela
2	Crna

3	Ostalo
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live

Question: *Gdje živite?*

Respondents who select “Other” are prompted to provide an open-text response, stored in live_3_TEXT, live_4_TEXT.

Value	Label
1	Urbano područje (npr. grad ili naselje)
2	Ruralno područje
3	Ostalo

born

Question: *Jeste li rođeni u Hrvatskoj?*

Respondents who select “No (not born in country)” are prompted to provide an open-text response, stored in born_2_TEXT.

Value	Label
1	Da
2	Ne

reg

Question: *U kojoj od makroregija živite?*

Value	Label
1	Zagrebačka
2	Riječka
3	Splitska
4	Osječka

socecon

Question: *Što najbolje opisuje vaš trenutni radni status?*

Value	Label
1	Zaposlen/a 30 sati tjedno ili više
2	Zaposlen/a manje od 30 sati tjedno
3	Samozaposlen/a

4	Umirovljenik/ica
5	Domaćin/ica
6	Student/ica
7	Nezaposlen/a
8	Radno onemogućen

relig_imp

Question: *Koliko je religija važna u vašem životu?*

Value	Label
1	Nimalo važna
2–9	(...)
10	Vrlo važna

relig_dom

Question: *Slijedite li neku religiju ili vjersku denominaciju?*

Value	Label
1	Da
2	Ne

relig_dom2

Question: *Kojoj religiji ili vjerskoj denominaciji pripadate?*

Respondents who select “Other” are prompted to provide an open-text response, stored in relig_dom2_7_TEXT, relig_dom2_8_TEXT, relig_dom2_11_TEXT.

Display logic: Displayed if relig_dom = 1 (respondent belongs to a religion or religious denomination).

Value	Label
1	Rimokatolička
2	Protestantska
3	Pravoslavna (ruska/grčka/itd.)
4	Židovstvo
5	Islam
6	Hinduizam
7	Budizam
8	Ostalo

house

Question: Što od sljedećeg najbolje opisuje vašu stambenu situaciju?

Value	Label
1	Stanujem u vlastitoj kući/stanu
2	Unajmljujem stambeni prostor
3	Stanujem s prijateljima ili obitelji
4	Nemam stambeno rješenje

inc_alt

Question: Ispod je popis DOHOTKA. Željeli bismo znati vaš KUĆNI DOHODAK. To jest, koji je ukupni dohodak svih članova kućanstva iz svih izvora, uključujući plaće, mirovine ili bilo koji drugi oblik prihoda, nakon obračunatih poreza (neto iznos).

Value	Label
1	A) Manje od €670 (neto) mjesečno
2	B) €670 do €999 (neto) mjesečno
3	C) €1000 do €1499 (neto) mjesečno
4	D) €1500 do €1999 (neto) mjesečno
5	E) €2000 do €2499 (neto) mjesečno
6	F) €2500 do €2999 (neto) mjesečno
7	G) €3000 do €3999 (neto) mjesečno
8	H) €4000 to €4999 (neto) mjesečno
9	I) Više od €5000 (neto) mjesečno

Populist Attitudes: People-Centrism

U kojoj se mjeri (ne) slažete sa sljedećim tvrdnjama?

Scale: 1 = Nikako se ne slažem, 2 = Ne slažem se, 3 = Niti se slažem niti se ne slažem, 4 = Slažem se, 5 = U potpunosti se slažem. Prefer not to answer was offered but excluded from export.

Variable	Item
peoplec_pre_1	Političari bi uvijek trebali pažljivo slušati o problemima ljudi.
peoplec_pre_2	Političarima nije potrebno provoditi vrijeme među običnim ljudima da bi dobro obavljali svoj posao.
peoplec_pre_3	Volja naroda trebala bi biti najviše načelo u politici ove zemlje.

Populist Attitudes: Anti-Elitism

U kojoj se mjeri (ne) slažete sa sljedećim tvrdnjama?

Scale: 1 = Nikako se ne slažem, 2 = Ne slažem se, 3 = Niti se slažem niti se ne slažem, 4 = Slažem se, 5 = U potpunosti se slažem. Prefer not to answer was offered but excluded from export.

Variable	Item
antie_pre_1	Vlada je uglavnom pod kontrolom nekoliko moćnih krugova koji gledaju samo svoje interese.
antie_pre_2	Državni službenici koriste svoj položaj da bi poboljšali živote ljudi.
antie_pre_3	Priličan broj ljudi na vlasti je korumpiran.

Populist Attitudes: Manicheanism

U kojoj se mjeri (ne) slažete sa sljedećim tvrdnjama?

Scale: 1 = U potpunosti se ne slažem, 2 = Ne slažem se, 3 = Niti se slažem niti ne slažem, 4 = Slažem se, 5 = U potpunosti se slažem. Prefer not to answer was offered but excluded from export.

Variable	Item
manich_pre_1	Možete prosuditi je li osoba dobra ili loša ako znate njezine političke stavove.
manich_pre_2	Ljudi s kojima se politički ne slažem nisu zli.
manich_pre_3	Ljudi s kojima se politički ne slažem su samo dezinformirani.

Trust in Institutions (Feeling Thermometer)

Kako biste ocijenili sljedeće grupe i organizacije? Ocjene između 51 stupnjeva i 100 stupnjeva znače da se osjećate povoljno i toplo prema grupi ili organizaciji. Ocjene između 0 stupnjeva i 49 stupnjeva znače da imate negativan stav prema ovoj grupi/organizaciji.

Scale: 0–100 feeling thermometer (0 = cold/unfavorable, 50 = neutral, 100 = warm/favorable). Prefer not to answer was offered but excluded from export.

Variable	Item
th_pre_1	Novinari
th_pre_4	Znanstvenici
th_pre_5	Sveučilišni profesori
th_pre_6	Državni službenici
th_pre_7	Sabor
th_pre_8	Europska unija
th_pre_9	Političke stranke
th_pre_10	Velike kompanije
th_pre_11	Kapitalisti

th_pre_12	Policija
th_pre_13	Vojska
th_pre_16	Katolička crkva
th_pre_17	Sjevernoatlantski pakt (NATO)
th_pre_18	Međunarodni monetarni fond (MMF)

Nationalism

Neki ljudi kažu da sljedeće karakteristike smatraju bitnima za opis istinskog Hrvata/ice. Drugi kažu da nisu važne.

Scale: 1 = Posve nevažno, 2 = Uglavnom nevažno, 3 = Uglavnom važno, 4 = Veoma važno. Prefer not to answer was offered but excluded from export.

Variable	Item
nat_pre_1	Biti rođen u Hrvatskoj.
nat_pre_2	Imati hrvatsko porijeklo.
nat_pre_3	Govoriti hrvatski jezik.
nat_pre_4	Živjeti u skladu s hrvatskom kulturom.

Attitudes Towards Democracy

dem_pre

Question: *Opisat ćemo različite vrste političkih sustava i pitati vas što mislite o svakom kao načinu upravljanja vašom zemljom. Kako biste ocijenili svaki od načina upravljanja svojoj zemljom?*

Value	Label
1	Posve nevažno
2–9	(...)
10	Veoma važno

Opisat ćemo različite vrste političkih sustava i pitati vas što mislite o svakom kao načinu upravljanja vašom zemljom. Za svaki, biste li rekli da je vrlo dobar, prilično dobar, prilično loš ili vrlo loš način upravljanja vašom zemljom?

Scale: 1 = Vrlo dobar, 2 = Prilično dobar, 3 = Prilično loš, 4 = Veoma loš. Prefer not to answer was offered but excluded from export.

Variable	Item
polsys_pre_1	Imati moćnog vođu koji se ne zamara vladom i izborima.
polsys_pre_2	Imati stručnjake, a ne vladu, koji bi donosili odluke prema tome što oni ocjenjuju kao najbolje za državu.

polsys_pre_3	Imati demokratski politički sustav.
polsys_pre_4	Imati vojsku koja upravlja državom.

Political Orientation and Ideology

ideol_self

Question: *U političkim pitanjima ljudi govore o „ljevici“ i „desnici“. Gdje biste se Vi sa svojim uvjerenjem smjestili na ovoj ljestvici?*

Value	Label
1	Lijevo
2–9	(...)
10	Desno

ideol_respo

Question: *Kamo biste smjestili svoje poglede od 1 do 10?*

Value	Label
1	Natjecanje je dobro.
2–9	(...)
10	Natjecanje je štetno

ideol_eq

Question: *Kamo biste smjestili svoje poglede na ovoj ljestvici?*

Value	Label
1	Treba povećati privatno vlasništvo nad poduzećima.
2–9	(...)
10	Razlike u plaćama bi trebale biti što veće, kako bi se potaknulo zalaganje pojedinaca.

ideol_own

Question: *Kamo biste smjestili svoje poglede na ovoj ljestvici?*

Value	Label
1	Treba povećati privatno vlasništvo nad poduzećima.
2–9	(...)
10	Treba povećati državno vlasništvo nad poduzećima.

eu

Question: *Neki kažu da bi se proširenje Europske unije trebalo nastaviti dalje. Drugi kažu da je već otišlo predaleko.*

Value	Label
1	Trebalo bi ići puno dalje
2	Trebalo bi ići malo dalje
3	Trebalo bi ostati kako je
4	EU se već proširila više nego što je potrebno
5	Dalje proširenje bilo bi jako pretjerano

Authoritarian Attitudes

U kojoj se mjeri (ne) slažete sa sljedećim tvrdnjama?

Scale: 1 = Nikako se ne slažem, 2 = Ne slažem se, 3 = Niti se slažem niti se ne slažem, 4 = Slažem se, 5 = U potpunosti se slažem. Prefer not to answer was offered but excluded from export.

Variable	Item
al_1	Mladi danas nemaju dovoljno poštovanja prema tradicionalnim vrijednostima.
al_2	Za neke zločine, smrtna kazna je najprimjerenijakazna.
al_3	Škole bi trebale učiti djecu da poštuju autoritet.

Political Mobilization

Ispod su različiti oblici političke akcije koje ljudi mogu poduzeti.

Scale: 1 = Učinio/la sam, 2 = Učinio/la bih, 3 = Nikad ne bih učinio/la. Prefer not to answer was offered but excluded from export.

Variable	Item
mobi_1	Učinio/la sam
mobi_2	Pridruživanje bojkotu
mobi_4	Sudjelovanje na zakonski odobrenim demonstracijama
mobi_6	Pridruživanje štrajku

Political Interest and Voting**pol_i**

Question: *Koliko ste zainteresirani za politiku?*

Value	Label
-------	-------

1	Veoma zainteresiran/a
2	Donekle zainteresiran/a
3	Ne baš zainteresiran/a
4	Nisam uopće zainteresiran/a

pol_vote

Question: *S obzirom na nadolazeće nacionalne izbore, za KOJU STRANKU s ovog popisa biste glasali? Respondents who select “Other” are prompted to provide an open-text response, stored in pol_vote_5_TEXT.*

Value	Label
1	Hrvatska-demokratska zajednica (HDZ)
2	Socijaldemokratska partija (SDP)
3	Možemo
4	MOST
5	Domovinski Pokret
6	Centar
7	Fokus
8	Dalija Orešković i ljudi s imenom i prezimenom
9	Građansko-liberalni savez (Glas)
10	Hrvatska narodna stranka (HNS)
11	Hrvatska socijalno-liberalna stranka (HSLŠ)
12	Istarski demokratski sabor (IDS)
13	Hrvatski suverenisti
14	Hrvatska seljačka stranka (HSS)
15	Nezavisna platforma Sjevera
16	Hrvatska stranka umirovljenika
17	Pravo i pravda
18	Samostalna demokratska srpska stranka (SDSS)
19	Nezavisni
20	Drugo

Satisfaction and Alienation

sat

Question: *Sveukupno gledajući, koliko ste zadovoljni sa svojim životom ovih dana?*

Value	Label
-------	-------

1	Uopće ne
2–9	(...)
10	Zadovoljan

alien

Question: *Neki ljudi osjećaju da imaju potpunu slobodu i kontrolu nad svojim životima, a drugi osjećaju da ono što čine nema nikakvog stvarnog utjecaja na ono što im se događa. Molimo naznačite na ovoj ljestvici koliko slobode izbora i kontrole mislite da imate nad svojim životom?*

Value	Label
1	Uopće ne
2–9	(...)
10	Najvećim dijelom

cap

Question: *U kojoj se mjeri (ne) slažete sa sljedećom izjavom? U svom svakodnevnom životu imam vrlo malo prilika pokazati koliko sam sposoban/na.*

Value	Label
1	Nikako se ne slažem
2	Ne slažem se
3	Niti se slažem niti se ne slažem
4	Slažem se
5	U potpunosti se slažem

Neighborhood Conditions

Koliko se često u vašem susjedstvu događaju sljedeće stvari?

Scale: 1 = Izuzetno često, 2 = Često, 3 = Ponekad, 4 = Rijetko, 5 = Nikad. Prefer not to answer was offered but excluded from export.

Variable	Item
hood_1	Pljačke
hood_2	Konзумiranje alkohola na ulicama
hood_3	Policija se miješa u privatni život ljudi

Economic Perceptions

econ

Question: Što mislite o stanju ekonomije ovih dana u Hrvatskoj? Biste li rekli da je stanje ekonomije dobro, ni dobro ni loše, ili loše?

Value	Label
1	Dobro
2	Ni dobro ni loše
3	Loše

econg

Question: Ako mislite da je stanje ekonomije dobro, koliko je po Vašem sudu dobro?

Display logic: Displayed if econ = 1 (respondent said economy is good).

Value	Label
1	Dobro
2	Izuzetno dobro

econb

Question: Ako mislite da je stanje ekonomije loše, koliko je po Vašem sudu loše?

Display logic: Displayed if econ = 3 (respondent said economy is bad).

Value	Label
1	Loše
2	Izuzetno loše

fsit

Question: Koliko ste zabrinuti za trenutnu financijsku situaciju vas i vaše obitelji?

Value	Label
1	Nimalo
2	Malo
3	Umjereno
4	Vrlo
5	Izuzetno

Sexual Harassment Attitudes

harass

Question: Mislite li da je javna/medijska pozornost koju se posvećuje seksualnom uznemiravanju pretjerana, nedovoljna, ili je umjerena?

Value	Label
1	Pretjerana je
2	Umjerena je
3	Nije dovoljna

harass2

Question: *Mislite li da je pozornost koju se posvećuje seksualnom uznemiravanju malo ili jako pretjerana?*

Display logic: Displayed if harass = 1 (respondent said attention has gone too far).

Value	Label
1	Malo pretjerana
2	Jako pretjerana

harass3

Question: *Mislite li da pozornost koju se posvećuje seksualnom uznemiravanju nije dovoljna ili ni približno dovoljna?*

Display logic: Displayed if harass = 3 (respondent said attention has not gone far enough).

Value	Label
1	Nije dovoljna
2	Ni približno dovoljna

Immigration and Ethnic Relations

methnic

Question: *Da li povećanje broja ljudi različitih rasa i etničkih skupina u Hrvatskoj čini ovu zemlju povoljnijom za život, nepovoljnijom za život, ili to ne čini nikakvu razliku?*

Value	Label
1	Povoljnijom
2	Ne čini razliku
3	Nepovoljnijom

methnic2

Question: *Da li povećanje broja ljudi različitih rasa i etničkih skupina čini Hrvatsku malo povoljnijom za život ili puno povoljnijom za život?*

Display logic: Displayed if methnic = 1 (respondent said diversity makes country better).

Value	Label
1	Malo povoljnijom
2	Puno povoljnijom

methnic3

Question: *Da li povećanje broja ljudi različitih rasa i etničkih skupina čini Hrvatsku malo nepovoljnijom za život ili puno nepovoljnijom za život?*

Display logic: Displayed if methnic = 3 (respondent said diversity makes country worse).

Value	Label
1	Malo nepovoljnijom
2	Puno nepovoljnijom

COVID-19 and Vaccination

cov

Question: *Jeste li bili zaraženi koronavirusom između 2020. i 2022. godine?*

Value	Label
1	Da
2	Ne

vac

Question: *Jeste li cijepljeni protiv koronavirusa?*

Value	Label
1	Da
2	Ne

die

Question: *Je li član vaše obitelji preminuo kao direktan rezultat zaraze koronavirusom između 2020. i 2022. godine?*

Value	Label
1	Da
2	Ne

die2

Question: *Koliko je članova vaše obitelji preminulo kao direktan rezultat zaraze koronavirusom između 2020. i 2022. godine?*

Display logic: Displayed if die = 1 (respondent said yes, a family member died of COVID).

Value	Label
1	1
2	2
3	3
4	4
5	Više od 5

vacrisk

Question: *Mislite li da zdravstvene koristi cijepljenja općenito pretežu nad rizicima, pretežu li rizici nad koristima, ili nema razlike?*

Value	Label
1	Koristi pretežu nad rizicima
2	Rizici pretežu nad koristima
3	Nema razlike

vacrisk2

Question: *Jesu li zdravstvene koristi cijepljenja puno veće ili nešto veće?*

Display logic: Displayed if vacrisk = 1 (respondent said benefits outweigh risks).

Value	Label
1	Puno veće
2	Nešto veće

vacrisk3

Question: *Jesu li rizici cijepljenja puno veći ili nešto veći?*

Display logic: Displayed if vacrisk = 2 (respondent said risks outweigh benefits).

Value	Label
1	Puno veći
2	Nešto veći

covsci

Question: *Općenito, koliko je važno da znanost igra ulogu u donošenju vladinih odluka o koronavirusu?*

Value	Label
1	Nimalo važno
2	Malo važno
3	Umjereno važno
4	Vrlo važno
5	Izuzetno važno

covforce

Question: *Neki ljudi misle da cijepljenje protiv Covid-19 treba biti zakonski obvezno. Drugi misle da pojedinci trebaju imati pravo odabrati hoće li se cijepiti ili ne. Što je bliže vašem mišljenju?*

Value	Label
1	Svi bi trebali biti cijepljeni
2	Pojedinac bi trebao odlučiti

Neki ljudi misle da vlada treba kažnjavati pojedince koji se odluče ne cijepiti. Drugi se protive tome.

Scale: 1 = Snažno podržavam, 2 = Donekle podržavam, 3 = Niti podržavam niti ne podržavam, 4 = Donekle se protivim, 5 = Snažno se protivim. Prefer not to answer was offered but excluded from export.

Variable	Item
covpen_1	Financijska / novčana kazna
covpen_2	Jednomjesečna zatvorska kazna
covpen_3	Privremeno oduzimanje skrbništva nad djecom
covpen_4	Gubitak posla

Social Class

The social class variables in this survey are based on Erik Olin Wright's class analysis framework. Respondents are classified according to their position in relations of production, with employees subdivided by authority over other workers and possession of scarce skills or credentials. The questions follow a branching structure: all respondents who are currently employed (socecon = 1, 2, or 3) receive the class battery. All respondents, regardless of employment status, are asked about subjective class identification (class_self).

class

Question: *Jeste li zaposleni kod nekog drugog, samozaposleni ili radite bez plaće u svojoj tvrtki?*
Display logic: Displayed if socecon = 1, 2, or 3 (respondent is currently employed full-time, part-time, or self-employed).

Value	Label
1	Zaposlen/a od strane nekog drugog
2	Samozaposlen/a
3	Radim bez plaće

class_sect

Question: Radite li za državne ili javne službe, privatni sektor, ili neprofitnu organizaciju?

Display logic: Displayed if class = 1 (respondent is employed by someone else).

Value	Label
1	Državne ili javne službe
2	Privatne poslovne organizacije ili kompanije
3	Neprofitna organizacija / treći sektor

class_own

Question: Jeste li vlasnik ili suvlasnik neke tvrtke?

Display logic: Displayed if class_sect = 2 (private sector), class = 2 (self-employed), or class = 3 (works without pay).

Value	Label
1	Da
2	Ne

class_own2

Question: Jeste li partner u navedenoj firmi ili posjedujete dionice?

Display logic: Displayed if class_own = 1 (respondent is an owner or part-owner).

Value	Label
1	Samo posjedujem dionice
2	Vlasnik / partner

class_emp

Question: Ima li ova tvrtka plaćene zaposlenike? To jest, zapošljava li članove koji nisu iz obitelji, a rade za plaću?

Display logic: Displayed if class = 2 (self-employed) or class = 3 (works without pay).

Value	Label
-------	-------

1	Da
2	Ne

class_emp_no

Question: *Koliko je otprilike ljudi zaposleno u ovoj tvrtki?*

Display logic: Displayed if class_own2 = 2 (actual owner/partner) or class_emp = 1 (business has paid employees).

Value	Label
1	Nema zaposlenih
2	1 - 20 zaposlenih
3	Više od 20 zaposlenih

class_skill

Question: *Kad bi se za vaše radno mjesto raspisivalo javni natječaj, koja bi bila minimalna razina obrazovanja ili obuke potrebna za nekoga tko bi radio vaš posao?*

Display logic: Displayed if socecon = 1, 2, or 3 (respondent is currently employed).

Value	Label
1	Nisu potrebne kvalifikacije
2	Srednjoškolsko obrazovanje
3	50 ili više sati specifične obuke za rad
4	Sveučilišna diploma prvog stupnja
5	Postdiplomska kvalifikacija (npr. magisterij, doktorat ili bilo koja druga kvalifikacija potrebna nakon završenog preddiplomskog studija)

class_sup

Question: *Kao službeni dio vašeg posla, nadgledate li rad drugih zaposlenika ili im govorite što da rade?*

Display logic: Displayed if class = 1 (respondent is employed by someone else).

Value	Label
1	Da
2	Ne

class_man

Question: *Sljedeće pitanje tiče se donošenja odluka na vašem radnom mjestu; to jest, donošenja odluka o stvarima kao što su proizvodi ili usluge koje pružate, ukupan broj zaposlenih, proračuni itd.*

Display logic: Displayed if class = 1 (respondent is employed by someone else).

Value	Label
1	Da
2	Ne

Display logic: Displayed if class_sup = 1 (respondent supervises other employees).

U sklopu vašega posla, jeste li izravno odgovorni za nešto od navedenog?

Scale: 1 = Da, 2 = Ne. Prefer not to answer was offered but excluded from export.

Variable	Item
class_sup2_2	Imate li utjecaj na dodjeljivanje povišice ili promocije zaposlenima?
class_sup2_3	Imate li utjecaj na otpuštanje ili suspenziju zaposlenih?

class_self

Question: *Ljudi ponekad sebe opisuju kao pripadnike radničke klase, srednje klase ili više ili niže klase. Kako biste opisali sebe?*

Value	Label
1	Viša klasa i viša srednja klasa
2	Srednja i niža srednja klasa
3	Radnička klasa
4	Niža klasa

Display logic: Displayed if class_man = 1 (respondent participates in policy-making decisions).

Kao dio vašeg posla, sudjelujete li u bilo kojoj od sljedećih vrsta donošenja odluka? To uključuje i davanje savjeta u procesu donošenja odluka.

Scale: 1 = Da, 2 = Ne. Prefer not to answer was offered but excluded from export.

Variable	Item
class_man2_1	Odluke o povećanju ili smanjenju ukupnog broja zaposlenih na mjestu gdje radite?
class_man2_2	Odluke koje se tiču proračuna na mjestu gdje radite?

Germany

Companion Codebook

Language: German

Data Source: Qualtrics

Sample: 2,094

Question text and response labels are shown in the original language as administered to respondents.

Germany

Survey Metadata

StartDate

EndDate

Duration..in.seconds.

consent

Question: *Bei dieser Umfrage geht es um Ihre Ansichten zur Politik und zu Organisationen während der COVID-19-Pandemie und wie es um die Beteiligung der Bürger:innen bestellt war. Ihre Teilnahme ist uns wichtig, damit wir die öffentliche Meinung zu diesen Themen besser verstehen können. Sie sind jedoch nicht verpflichtet, die folgenden Fragen zu beantworten und können die Umfrage jederzeit abbrechen. Ihre Antworten bleiben anonym. Wir wissen Ihre Zeit zu schätzen und danken Ihnen sehr für die sorgfältige ...*

Value	Label
1	Ich stimme der Teilnahme an der Umfrage zu
2	Ich lehne die Teilnahme ab

Demographics

gender

Question: *Was ist Ihr Geschlecht?*

Respondents who select "Other" are prompted to provide an open-text response, stored in gender_4_TEXT.

Value	Label
1	Männlich
2	Weiblich
3	Nicht-binär
4	Andere

age

Question: *Wie alt sind Sie?*

Value	Label
1	18

2	19
3	20
...	(value = age - 17)
75	92
76	93
83	100
93	Möchte nicht antworten

Note: Coding follows the pattern value = age - 17 (e.g., 1 = 18 years old, 50 = 67 years old). The value 93 is reserved for “Möchte nicht antworten” and should be treated as missing.

edu

Question: Was ist der höchste Studienabschluss, den Sie erreicht haben?

Value	Label
1	Kein Studienabschluss
2	Zwischenprüfung, Vordiplom
3	Diplom einer Verwaltungs-/Fachhochschule
4	Diplom einer Berufsakademie
5	Bachelor einer Verwaltungs-/Fachhochschule
6	Bachelor einer Berufsakademie
7	Bachelor einer Universität, Kunst-, Musik- oder pädagogischen Hochschule
8	Master einer Verwaltungs-/Fachhochschule
9	Master einer Berufsakademie
10	Diplom, Magister, Staatsexamen einer Universität, Kunst-, Musik oder pädagogischen Hochschule
11	Master oder Aufbaustudium einer Universität, Kunst-, Musikoder pädagogischen Hochschule

live

Question: Wo wohnen Sie?

Respondents who select “Other” are prompted to provide an open-text response, stored in live_3_TEXT, live_4_TEXT.

Value	Label
1	In einer Stadt
2	Auf dem Land
3	Woanders

born

Question: *Sind Sie in Deutschland (einschließlich der Deutschen Demokratischen Republik) geboren?*
 Respondents who select “No (not born in country)” are prompted to provide an open-text response, stored in `born_2_TEXT`.

Value	Label
1	Ja
2	Nein

reg

Question: *In welchem Bundesland wohnen Sie?*

Value	Label
1	Baden-Württemberg
2	Bayern
3	Berlin
4	Brandenburg
5	Bremen
6	Hamburg
7	Hessen
8	Mecklenburg-Vorpommern
9	Niedersachsen
10	Nordrhein-Westfalen
11	Rheinland-Pfalz
12	Saarland
13	Sachsen
14	Sachsen-Anhalt
15	Schleswig-Holstein
16	Thüringen

socecon

Question: *Sind Sie zurzeit berufstätig oder nicht?*

Value	Label
1	30 Stunden in der Woche oder mehr
2	Weniger als 30 Stunden in der Woche
3	Selbstständig
4	Rentner, Ruhestand

5	Hausfrau, Hausmann ohne weitere sonstige Beschäftigung
6	Schüler, Student, in Ausbildung
7	Arbeitslos
8	Dauerhaft arbeitsunfähig wegen einer Behinderung

relig_imp

Question: *Wie wichtig ist Gott in Ihrem Leben?*

Value	Label
1	Überhaupt nicht wichtig
2–9	(...)
10	Sehr wichtig

relig_dom

Question: *Gehören Sie einer Religionsgemeinschaft an?*

Value	Label
1	Ja
2	Nein

relig_dom2

Question: *Welcher Religionsgemeinschaft gehören Sie an?*

Respondents who select “Other” are prompted to provide an open-text response, stored in relig_dom2_7_TEXT, relig_dom2_8_TEXT, relig_dom2_11_TEXT.

Display logic: Displayed if relig_dom = 1 (respondent belongs to a religion or religious denomination).

Value	Label
1	Der römisch-katholischen Kirche
2	Der evangelischen Kirche (ohne Freikirchen)
3	Einer evangelischen Freikirche
4	Der griechisch-orthodoxen Kirche
5	Der russisch-orthodoxen Kirche
6	Dem Islam
7	Einer anderen Religionsgemeinschaft

house

Question: *Welche der folgenden Aussagen beschreibt Ihre Wohnsituation am besten?*

Value	Label
1	Ich besitze mein eigenes Haus oder Wohnung
2	Ich wohne zur Miete
3	Ich wohne bei Verwandten oder Freunden
4	Ich bin wohnungslos

inc_alt

Question: Folgend sehen Sie eine Liste mit Einkommensklassen. Bitte geben Sie an, in welcher Klasse sich Ihr Haushalt befindet, wenn Sie das Nettoeinkommen aller Haushaltsmitglieder zusammenzählen: Löhne, Renten und andere Einkommen nach allen Abzügen für Steuern und Sozialversicherungen. Ungefähr im MONAT A Unter €800 B €800 to €1199 C €1200 to €1599 D €1600 to €1999 E €2000 to €2399 F €2400 to €3199 G €3200 to €3999 H €4000 to €4799 I €4800 to €7999 J €8000 to €11,999 K Mehr als €12,000

Value	Label
1	A) Unter €800 pro Monat
2	B) €800 to €1199 pro Monat
3	C) €1200 to €1599 pro Monat
4	D) €1600 to €1999 pro Monat
5	E) €2000 to €2399 pro Monat
6	F) €2400 to €3199 pro Monat
7	G) €3200 to €3999 pro Monat
8	H) €4000 to €4799 pro Monat
9	I) €4800 to €7999 pro Monat
10	J) €8000 to €11,999 pro Monat
11	K) Mehr als €12,000 pro Monat

Populist Attitudes: People-Centrism

Wie sehr stimmen Sie den folgenden Aussagen zu?

Scale: 1 = stimme überhaupt nicht zu, 2 = stimme nicht zu, 3 = stimme weder zu noch nicht zu, 4 = stimme zu, 5 = stimme voll und ganz zu. Prefer not to answer was offered but excluded from export.

Variable	Item
peoplec_pre_1	Politiker:innen sollten immer genau zuhören, wenn es um die Probleme der Menschen geht.
peoplec_pre_2	Politiker:innen müssen keine Zeit mit den ganz normalen Bürger:innen verbringen, um gute Arbeit zu leisten.
peoplec_pre_3	Der Wille des Volkes sollte der wichtigste Grundsatz in der Politik dieses Landes sein.

Populist Attitudes: Anti-Elitism

Wie sehr stimmen Sie den folgenden Aussagen zu?

Scale: 1 = stimme überhaupt nicht zu, 2 = stimme nicht zu, 3 = stimme weder zu noch nicht zu, 4 = stimme zu, 5 = stimme voll und ganz zu. Prefer not to answer was offered but excluded from export.

Variable	Item
antie_pre_1	Das Land wird von einigen wenigen großen Interessengruppen regiert, die sich nur um sich selbst kümmern.
antie_pre_2	Regierungsbeamt:innen nutzen ihre Macht, um das Leben der Menschen zu verbessern.
antie_pre_3	Etliche Mitglieder der Regierung sind Betrüger:innen.

Populist Attitudes: Manicheanism

Wie sehr stimmen Sie den folgenden Aussagen zu?

Scale: 1 = stimme überhaupt nicht zu, 2 = stimme nicht zu, 3 = stimme weder zu noch nicht zu, 4 = stimme zu, 5 = stimme voll und ganz zu. Prefer not to answer was offered but excluded from export.

Variable	Item
manich_pre_1	Ob eine Person gut oder schlecht ist, kann man beurteilen, wenn man ihre politischen Ansichten kennt.
manich_pre_2	Die Menschen, mit denen ich politisch nicht einer Meinung bin, sind nicht automatisch böse oder schlechte Menschen.
manich_pre_3	Die Menschen, mit denen ich politisch nicht einer Meinung bin, sind bloß falsch informiert.

Trust in Institutions (Feeling Thermometer)

Wie beurteilen Sie die folgenden Gruppen und Organisationen? Bewertungen zwischen 51 und 100 Grad bedeuten, dass Sie diese Gruppe/Organisation als positiv empfinden. Bewertungen zwischen 0 und 49 Grad bedeuten, dass Sie diese Gruppe/Organisation als negativ empfinden.

Scale: 0–100 feeling thermometer (0 = cold/unfavorable, 50 = neutral, 100 = warm/favorable). Prefer not to answer was offered but excluded from export.

Variable	Item
th_pre_1	Die Presse
th_pre_4	Die Wissenschaft
th_pre_5	Hochschulprofessoren
th_pre_6	Die öffentliche Verwaltung
th_pre_7	Der Bundestag
th_pre_8	Die Europäische Union (EU)

th_pre_9	Die politischen Parteien
th_pre_10	Große Wirtschaftsunternehmen
th_pre_11	Kapitalisten
th_pre_12	Die Polizei
th_pre_13	Die Bundeswehr
th_pre_16	Die Kirchen
th_pre_17	Die NATO
th_pre_18	Der Internationale Währungsfonds

Nationalism

Einige Menschen sagen, die folgenden Dinge seien wichtig, um wirklich deutsch zu sein. Andere dagegen sagen, sie seien nicht wichtig.

Scale: 1 = Überhaupt nicht wichtig, 2 = Nicht wichtig, 3 = Ziemlich wichtig, 4 = Sehr wichtig. Prefer not to answer was offered but excluded from export.

Variable	Item
nat_pre_1	In Deutschland geboren zu sein
nat_pre_2	Deutsche Vorfahren zu haben
nat_pre_3	Deutsch sprechen zu können
nat_pre_4	Nach der deutschen Lebensart und -weise zu leben

Attitudes Towards Democracy

dem_pre

Question: *Wie wichtig ist es für Sie, in einem Land zu leben, das demokratisch regiert wird? Für Ihre Antwort benutzen Sie bitte diese Skala, auf der 1 für "überhaupt nicht wichtig" und 10 für "absolut wichtig" steht.*

Value	Label
1	Überhaupt nicht wichtig
2–9	(...)
10	Absolut wichtig

Ich werde Ihnen nun verschiedene Typen von politischen Systemen beschreiben und fragen, was Sie von jedem einzelnen als Regierungsform für unser Land halten.

Scale: 1 = Sehr gut, 2 = Ziemlich gut, 3 = Ziemlich schlecht, 4 = Sehr schlecht. Prefer not to answer was offered but excluded from export.

Variable	Item
polsys_pre_1	Man sollte eine:n starke:n Staatschef:in haben, welche:r sich nicht um ein Parlament und um Wahlen kümmern muss.
polsys_pre_2	Anstelle der Regierung sollten Experten:innen entscheiden, was das Beste für das Land ist.
polsys_pre_3	Man sollte ein demokratisches politisches System haben.
polsys_pre_4	Das Militär sollte das Land regieren.

Political Orientation and Ideology

ideol_self

Question: *In der Politik spricht man von "links" und "rechts". Wie würden Sie ganz allgemein Ihren eigenen politischen Standort beschreiben: Wo auf dieser Skala würden Sie sich selbst einstufen?*

Value	Label
1	Links
2–9	(...)
10	Rechts

ideol_respo

Question: *Wo würden Sie Ihre eigenen Ansichten auf dieser Skala einordnen?*

Value	Label
1	Wettbewerb ist gut
2–9	(...)
10	Der Staat sollte mehr Verantwortung dafür übernehmen, dass jede:r abgesichert ist

ideol_eq

Question: *Wo würden Sie Ihre eigenen Ansichten auf dieser Skala einordnen?*

Value	Label
1	Mehr staatliche Unternehmen sollten privatisiert werden
2–9	(...)
10	Es sollte größere Anreize für persönliche Leistung geben

ideol_own

Question: *Wo würden Sie Ihre eigenen Ansichten auf dieser Skala einordnen?*

Value	Label
1	Mehr staatliche Unternehmen sollten privatisiert werden

2-9	(...)
10	Mehr private Unternehmen sollten verstaatlicht werden

eu

Question: *Manche meinen, dass die Erweiterung der Europäischen Union weiter gehen soll. Andere dagegen sagen, sie sei bereits zu weit gegangen.*

Value	Label
1	Sollte weiter gehen
2-9	(...)
10	Ist bereits zu weit gegangen

Authoritarian Attitudes

Wie sehr stimmen Sie den folgenden Aussagen zu oder nicht zu?

Scale: 1 = stimme überhaupt nicht zu, 2 = stimme nicht zu, 3 = stimme weder zu noch nicht zu, 4 = stimme zu, 5 = stimme voll und ganz zu. Prefer not to answer was offered but excluded from export.

Variable	Item
al_1	Die Jugend von heute hat zu wenig Respekt vor traditionellen Werten.
al_2	Für manche Verbrechen ist die Todesstrafe die angemessene Strafe.
al_3	Die Schulen sollten die Kinder lehren, Autoritäten zu gehorchen.

Political Mobilization

Im Folgenden sind verschiedene Formen politischen Handelns aufgeführt, an denen Menschen teilhaben können. Bitte teilen Sie uns mit, ob Sie eines dieser Dinge getan haben, ob Sie es tun würden oder unter keinen Umständen jemals tun würden.

Scale: 1 = Schon einmal beteiligt, 2 = Vielleicht einmal tun, 3 = Ich würde das unter keinen Umständen tun. Prefer not to answer was offered but excluded from export.

Variable	Item
mobi_1	Schon einmal beteiligt
mobi_2	An einem Boykott teilnehmen
mobi_4	An einer genehmigten Demonstration teilnehmen
mobi_6	An einem Streik teilnehmen

Political Interest and Voting**pol_i**

Question: *Wie stark interessieren Sie sich für Politik? Sind Sie...*

Value	Label
1	Sehr interessiert
2	Etwas interessiert
3	Kaum interessiert
4	Überhaupt nicht interessiert

pol_vote

Question: *Wenn morgen Bundestagswahlen wären, welche Partei auf dieser Liste würden Sie wählen? Respondents who select "Other" are prompted to provide an open-text response, stored in pol_vote_5_TEXT.*

Value	Label
1	FDP
2	CDU
3	AfD
4	SPD
5	Bündnis 90/Die Grünen
6	Die Linke
7	Bündnis Sarah Wagenknecht
8	Andere

Satisfaction and Alienation

sat

Question: *Wenn Sie alles in Ihrem Leben berücksichtigen, wie zufrieden sind Sie insgesamt zurzeit mit Ihrem Leben?*

Value	Label
1	Überhaupt nicht zufrieden
2–9	(...)
10	Völlig zufrieden

alien

Question: *Einige Leute meinen, dass sie ihr Leben völlig frei selbst bestimmen. Andere meinen, dass sie nur wenig Einfluss darauf haben, was mit ihnen geschieht. Bitte benutzen Sie diese Skala um anzugeben, wieviel Entscheidungsfreiheit und Einfluss Sie nach Ihrem Empfinden darauf haben, wie Ihr weiteres Leben abläuft?*

Value	Label
1	Überhaupt keine Freiheit
2–9	(...)
10	Völlige Freiheit

cap

Question: *Inwieweit stimmen Sie der folgenden Aussagen zu oder nicht zu? "In meinem Alltag habe ich kaum Gelegenheit zu zeigen, was ich kann."*

Value	Label
1	stimme überhaupt nicht zu
2	stimme nicht zu
3	stimme weder zu noch nicht zu
4	stimme zu
5	stimme voll und ganz zu

Neighborhood Conditions

Wie häufig kommen die folgenden Dinge in Ihrer Nachbarschaft vor?

Scale: 1 = sehr oft, 2 = häufig, 3 = manchmal, 4 = selten, 5 = nie. Prefer not to answer was offered but excluded from export.

Variable	Item
hood_1	Raubüberfälle
hood_2	Alkoholkonsum auf der Straße
hood_3	Einmischung der Polizei in das Privatleben von Personen

Economic Perceptions**econ**

Question: *Wie beurteilen Sie die aktuelle wirtschaftliche Lage in Deutschland? Würden Sie sagen, dass die wirtschaftliche Lage gut, weder gut noch schlecht oder schlecht ist?*

Value	Label
1	Gut
2	Weder gut noch schlecht
3	Schlecht

econg

Question: *Wie gut ist Ihrer Meinung nach die Wirtschaftslage?*

Display logic: Displayed if econ = 1 (respondent said economy is good).

Value	Label
1	Einigermaßen gut
2	Sehr gut
3	Äußerst gut

econb

Question: *Wie schlecht ist Ihrer Meinung nach die wirtschaftliche Lage?*

Display logic: Displayed if econ = 3 (respondent said economy is bad).

Value	Label
1	Einigermaßen schlecht
2	Sehr schlecht
3	Extrem schlecht

fsit

Question: *Was Sie und Ihre Familie betrifft, wie besorgt sind Sie über Ihre derzeitige finanzielle Situation?*

Value	Label
1	Überhaupt nicht
2	Ein wenig
3	Mäßig
4	Sehr
5	Extrem

Sexual Harassment Attitudes

harass

Question: *Glauben Sie, dass die Aufmerksamkeit für sexuelle Belästigung zu weit gegangen ist, nicht weit genug gegangen ist oder gerade richtig ist?*

Value	Label
1	Ging zu weit
2	Ist ungefähr richtig
3	Ging nicht weit genug

harass2

Question: *Glauben Sie, dass die Aufmerksamkeit für Themen wie sexuelle Belästigung ein wenig zu weit oder viel zu weit gegangen ist?*

Display logic: Displayed if harass = 1 (respondent said attention has gone too far).

Value	Label
1	Ist etwas zu weit gegangen
2	Ist viel zu weit gegangen

harass3

Question: *Glauben Sie, dass die Aufmerksamkeit für das Thema sexuelle Belästigung noch nicht weit genug geht, oder nicht annähernd weit genug?*

Display logic: Displayed if harass = 3 (respondent said attention has not gone far enough).

Value	Label
1	Ist noch nicht weit genug gegangen
2	Ist nicht annähernd weit genug gegangen

Immigration and Ethnic Relations**methnic**

Question: *Macht die Zunahme von Menschen verschiedener Nationalitäten und Ethnien in Deutschland dieses Land lebenswerter oder weniger lebenswert oder macht es gar keinen Unterschied?*

Value	Label
1	Lebenswerter
2	Macht keinen Unterschied
3	Weniger lebenswert

methnic2

Question: *Wird Deutschland durch die Zunahme von Menschen verschiedener Nationalitäten und Ethnien ein etwas lebenswerterer oder ein viel lebenswerterer Ort?*

Display logic: Displayed if methnic = 1 (respondent said diversity makes country better).

Value	Label
1	Etwas lebenswerter
2	Viel lebenswerterer

methnic3

Question: *Macht die wachsende Zahl von Menschen verschiedener Nationalitäten und Ethnien Deutschland zu einem etwas schlechteren oder zu einem viel schlechteren Ort zum Leben?*

Display logic: Displayed if methnic = 3 (respondent said diversity makes country worse).

Value	Label
1	Etwas schlechter
2	Viel schlechter

mig

Question: *Sind Ihre beiden Eltern in Deutschland geboren?*

Value	Label
1	Ja, meine Eltern sind beide in Deutschland geboren
2	Nein, mindestens ein Elternteil ist außerhalb Deutschlands geboren

mig2

Question: *Würden Sie sich selbst als Migrant:in bzw. Person mit Migrationshintergrund bezeichnen?*

Value	Label
1	Ja
2	Nein
3	keine Angabe

COVID-19 and Vaccination

cov

Question: *Waren Sie zwischen 2020 und 2022 an COVID-19 erkrankt?*

Value	Label
1	Ja
2	Nein

vac

Question: *Wurden Sie gegen COVID-19 geimpft?*

Value	Label
1	Ja
2	Nein

die

Question: *Ist jemand aus Ihrer Familie an COVID-19 gestorben?*

Value	Label
1	Ja
2	Nein

die2

Question: *Wie viele Ihrer Familienmitglieder sind an der Krankheit COVID-19 gestorben?*

Display logic: Displayed if die = 1 (respondent said yes, a family member died of COVID).

Value	Label
1	1
2	2
3	3
4	4
5	Mehr als 5

vacrisk

Question: *Ist der gesundheitliche Nutzen von Impfungen im Allgemeinen größer als die Risiken, sind die Risiken größer als der Nutzen oder gibt es keinen Unterschied?*

Value	Label
1	der Nutzen überwiegt die Risiken
2	die Risiken sind größer als der Nutzen
3	kein Unterschied

vacrisk2

Question: *Ist der gesundheitliche Nutzen von Impfungen viel größer oder nur geringfügig größer?*

Display logic: Displayed if vacrisk = 1 (respondent said benefits outweigh risks).

Value	Label
1	Viel größer
2	Nur geringfügig größer

vacrisk3

Question: *Sind die Risiken von Impfungen viel größer oder nur geringfügig größer?*

Display logic: Displayed if vacrisk = 2 (respondent said risks outweigh benefits).

Value	Label
1	Viel größer
2	Nur geringfügig größer

covsci

Question: *Wie wichtig sollte die Wissenschaft generell für staatliche Entscheidungen über COVID-19 sein?*

Value	Label
1	Überhaupt nicht wichtig
2	Ein wenig wichtig
3	Mäßig wichtig
4	Sehr wichtig
5	Äußerst wichtig

covforce

Question: *Einige sind der Meinung, dass die Impfung gegen COVID-19 gesetzlich vorgeschrieben werden sollte. Andere sind der Meinung, dass es dem Einzelnen überlassen bleiben sollte, ob er sich impfen lässt oder nicht. Was entspricht eher Ihrer Meinung?*

Value	Label
1	Jeder sollte geimpft werden
2	Jeder sollte selbst entscheiden

Einige sind der Meinung, dass die Regierung Personen bestrafen sollte, die sich nicht impfen lassen wollen. Andere sind dagegen. Würden Sie folgende Strafen für Impfverweigerer befürworten oder ablehnen?

Scale: 1 = Sehr befürworten, 2 = Etwas befürworten, 3 = Weder befürworten noch ablehnen, 4 = Etwas ablehnen, 5 = Stark ablehnen. Prefer not to answer was offered but excluded from export.

Variable	Item
covpen_1	Eine Geldstrafe / Bußgeld
covpen_2	Ein Monat Gefängnis
covpen_3	Vorübergehender Entzug des Sorgerechts für ihre Kinder
covpen_4	Verlust des Arbeitsplatzes

Social Class

The social class variables in this survey are based on Erik Olin Wright's class analysis framework. Respondents are classified according to their position in relations of production, with employees subdivided by authority over other workers and possession of scarce skills or credentials. The questions follow a branching structure: all respondents who are currently employed (socecon = 1, 2, or 3) receive the class battery. All respondents, regardless of employment status, are asked about subjective class identification (class_self).

class

Question: *Sind Sie bei einem Unternehmen angestellt oder sind Sie selbständig?*

Display logic: Displayed if socecon = 1, 2, or 3 (respondent is currently employed full-time, part-time, or self-employed).

Value	Label
1	Angestellt
2	Selbständig

class_sect

Question: *Für wen arbeiten Sie in ihrem derzeitigen Hauptberuf?*

Display logic: Displayed if class = 1 (respondent is employed by someone else).

Value	Label
1	Für den öffentlichen Dienst
2	Für ein privates Unternehmen
3	Für eine private gemeinnützige Organisation

class_own

Question: *Sind Sie Eigentümer:in oder Miteigentümer:in dieses Unternehmens?*

Display logic: Displayed if class_sect = 2 (private sector), class = 2 (self-employed), or class = 3 (works without pay).

Value	Label
1	Ja
2	Nein

class_own2

Question: *Sind Sie an diesem Unternehmen beteiligt oder besitzen Sie Anteile?*

Display logic: Displayed if class_own = 1 (respondent is an owner or part-owner).

Value	Label
1	besitze Aktien
2	Eigentümer:in/Gesellschafter:in

class_emp

Question: Hat der Betrieb bezahlte Mitarbeiter:innen? D.h. Nicht-Familienmitglieder, die für ein Gehalt arbeiten?

Display logic: Displayed if class = 2 (self-employed) or class = 3 (works without pay).

Value	Label
1	Ja
2	Nein

class_emp_no

Question: Wie viele Personen sind / waren bei Ihnen beschäftigt?

Display logic: Displayed if class_own2 = 2 (actual owner/partner) or class_emp = 1 (business has paid employees).

Value	Label
1	Keine
2	1-24
3	25 oder mehr

class_skill

Question: Wenn Ihre Stelle ausgeschrieben wäre, welches Mindestmaß an Bildung oder Ausbildung wäre für die Ausübung Ihrer Tätigkeit erforderlich?

Display logic: Displayed if socecon = 1, 2, or 3 (respondent is currently employed).

Value	Label
1	keine Qualifikation erforderlich
2	höhere Schulbildung
3	50 Stunden oder mehr berufsspezifische Ausbildung
4	Universitäts- oder Hochschulabschluss
5	Postgraduiertenabschluss (z. B. Master, PhD oder ein anderer Abschluss, der nach dem Grundstudium verlangt wird)

class_sup

Question: Gehört/gehörte es zu Ihrer beruflichen Tätigkeit, die Arbeit von Personen anzuleiten und zu beaufsichtigen?

Display logic: Displayed if class = 1 (respondent is employed by someone else).

Value	Label
-------	-------

1	Ja
2	Nein

class_man

Question: Die nächste Frage bezieht sich auf politische Entscheidungen an Ihrem Arbeitsplatz, d.h. Entscheidungen über Produkte oder Dienstleistungen, die Gesamtzahl der Beschäftigten, Budgets usw.
Display logic: Displayed if class = 1 (respondent is employed by someone else).

Value	Label
1	Ja
2	Nein

Display logic: Displayed if class_sup = 1 (respondent supervises other employees).

Sind Sie im Rahmen Ihrer Tätigkeit für einen der folgenden Punkte direkt verantwortlich?
 Scale: 1 = Ja, 2 = Nein. Prefer not to answer was offered but excluded from export.

Variable	Item
class_sup2_2	Haben Sie Einfluss auf die Gewährung von Gehaltserhöhungen oder Beförderungen?
class_sup2_3	Haben Sie Einfluss auf die Entlassung oder Suspendierung unterstellten MitarbeiterInnen?

class_self

Question: Manche Menschen bezeichnen sich selbst als Angehörige der Arbeiterklasse, der Mittelschicht, der Oberschicht oder der Unterschicht. Wie würden Sie sich selbst beschreiben?

Value	Label
1	Oberschicht
2	Mittelklasse
3	Arbeiterklasse
4	Unterschicht

Display logic: Displayed if class_man = 1 (respondent participates in policy-making decisions).

Sind Sie im Rahmen Ihrer Arbeit an einer der folgenden Entscheidungen beteiligt? Dazu gehört auch die Beratung von Entscheidungsträger:innen.

Scale: 1 = Ja, 2 = Nein. Prefer not to answer was offered but excluded from export.

Variable	Item
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class_man2_1	Entscheidungen über die Erhöhung oder Verringerung der Gesamtzahl der Beschäftigten an Ihrem Arbeitsplatz
class_man2_2	Entscheidungen über das Budget Ihres Arbeitsplatzes

Education: Country-Specific (Germany)

edu2

Question: Was ist der höchste berufliche Ausbildungsabschluss, den Sie erreicht haben?

Respondents who select "Other" are prompted to provide an open-text response, stored in edu2_11_TEXT.

Value	Label
1	Kein Ausbildungsabschluss
2	Abschlusszeugnis Berufsgrundbildungsjahr, Berufsfachschule (Berufliche Grundkenntnisse), medizinische Hilfsberufe (1-jährige Schulen des Gesundheitswesens)
3	beruflich-betriebliche Anlernzeit mit Abschlusszeugnis, aber keine Lehre; Teilfacharbeiterabschluss
4	Abschlusszeugnis für medizinische Assistenten, Krankenschwestern/ -pfleger (2- bis 3-jährige Schulen des Gesundheitswesens)
5	Laufbahnprüfung für den mittleren Dienst
6	abgeschlossene gewerbliche oder landwirtschaftliche Lehre
7	Abgeschlossene kaufmännische Lehre
8	berufsqualifizierender Abschluss einer Berufsfachschule/eines Kollegs
9	berufliche Zweitausbildung
10	Meister-/Techniker- oder gleichwertiger Fachschulabschluss (inkl. Fachschule der ehemaligen DDR); Abschluss einer Fachakademie (Bayern)
11	Anderer beruflicher Ausbildungsabschluss, und zwar (bitte hier eintragen):

Poland

Companion Codebook

Language: Polish

Data Source: Qualtrics

Sample: 2,086

Question text and response labels are shown in the original language as administered to respondents.

Poland

Survey Metadata

StartDate

EndDate

Duration..in.seconds.

consent

Question: *To badanie sondażowe dotyczy różnych organizacji, COVID-19, polityki i aktywności obywatelskiej. Pana/Pani udział jest ważny, aby pomóc nam lepiej zrozumieć poglądy opinii publicznej na te kwestie. Nie musi Pan/Pani jednak odpowiadać na żadne z poniższych pytań i w dowolnym momencie można zrezygnować z wypełniania ankiety. Pana/Pani odpowiedzi będą anonimowe. Doceniamy Pana/Pani czas i dziękujemy za udzielenie przemyślanych i szczerych odpowiedzi na każde z pytań w tym istotnym badaniu. W ramach...*

Value	Label
1	ZGADZAM SIĘ na udział w badaniu
2	ODMAWIAM udziału

Demographics

gender

Question: *Proszę podać swoją płć.*

Respondents who select "Other" are prompted to provide an open-text response, stored in gender_4_TEXT.

Value	Label
1	mężczyzna
2	kobieta
3	osoba niebinarna
4	inna

age

Question: *Ile ma Pan/Pani lat?*

Value	Label
1	18

2	19
3	20
...	(value = age - 17)
75	92
76	93
83	100
93	Wolę nie odpowiadać

Note: Coding follows the pattern value = age - 17 (e.g., 1 = 18 years old, 50 = 67 years old). The value 93 is reserved for “Wolę nie odpowiadać” and should be treated as missing.

edu

Question: Jaki jest najwyższy poziom wykształcenia, który Pan/i/ osiągnął/ła/?

Value	Label
1	bez wykształcenia szkolnego lub niepełne podstawowe
2	podstawowe
3	gimnazjalne
4	zasadnicze zawodowe lub zasadnicze branżowe
5	średnie (bez matury)
6	średnie (z maturą)
7	świadectwo ukończenia szkoły policealnej, pomaturalnej lub kolegium
8	tytuł licencjata lub inżyniera
9	tytuł magistra, lekarza lub równorzędny
10	stopień naukowy (co najmniej doktora)

ethnicity

Question: Jakie jest Pana/Pani pochodzenie etniczne? Proszę wybrać wszystkie, które mają zastosowanie.

Respondents who select “Other” are prompted to provide an open-text response, stored in ethnicity_2_TEXT, ethnicity_6_TEXT, ethnicity_7_TEXT, ethnicity_15_TEXT.

Value	Label
1	polskie
2	białoruskie
3	czeskie
4	karaimskie
5	litewskie
6	łemkowskie

7	niemieckie
8	ormiańskie
9	romskie
11	słowackie
12	tatarskie
13	ukraińskie
15	inne (podać jakie)

live

Question: *Gdzie Pan/Pani mieszka?*

Respondents who select “Other” are prompted to provide an open-text response, stored in live_3_TEXT, live_4_TEXT.

Value	Label
1	Obszar miejski (np. miasto)
2	Obszar wiejski
3	Inne

born

Question: *Czy urodził/a/ się Pan/i/ w Polsce?*

Respondents who select “No (not born in country)” are prompted to provide an open-text response, stored in born_2_TEXT.

Value	Label
1	tak
2	nie, proszę podać nazwę kraju urodzenia

reg

Question: *W jakim województwie Pan/i obecnie mieszka?*

Value	Label
1	dolnośląskie
2	kujawsko-pomorskie
3	lubelskie
4	lubuskie
5	łódzkie
6	małopolskie

7	mazowieckie
8	opolskie
9	podkarpackie
10	podlaskie
11	pomorskie
12	śląskie
13	świętokrzyskie
14	warmińsko-mazurskie
15	wielkopolskie
16	zachodniopomorskie

socecon

Question: *Czy obecnie pracuje Pan/i/ zarobkowo? Proszę wybrać określenie sytuacji zawodowej, które najlepiej pasuje do Pana/i/.*

Value	Label
1	Pracujący/a/ zarobkowo 30 godzin tygodniowo lub więcej
2	Pracujący/a/ zarobkowo mniej niż 30 godzin w tygodniu
3	Samozatrudniony/a/
4	Osoba na rencie/emeryturze
5	Osoba zajmująca się domem, nigdzie poza tym niezatrudniona
6	Student/ka/, uczeń/nica/
7	Bezrobotny/a/
8	Osoba z niepełnosprawnością

relig_imp

Question: *Na ile ważny jest Bóg w Pana/i/ życiu?*

Value	Label
1	w ogóle nieważny
2–9	(...)
10	bardzo ważny

relig_dom

Question: *Czy jest Pan/i/ wyznawcą jakiejś religii?*

Value	Label
-------	-------

1	tak
2	nie

relig_dom2

Question: *Jaka jest Pana/i/ religia lub wyznanie?*

Respondents who select “Other” are prompted to provide an open-text response, stored in relig_dom2_7_TEXT, relig_dom2_8_TEXT, relig_dom2_11_TEXT.

Display logic: Displayed if relig_dom = 1 (respondent belongs to a religion or religious denomination).

Value	Label
1	Rzymskokatolicka
2	Prawosławna
3	Świadkowie Jehowy
4	Protestantyzm
5	Ewangelicka
6	Grekokatolicka
8	Judaizm
9	Islam
10	Buddyzm
11	Inne

house

Question: *Które z poniższych określić najlepiej obrazuje Pana/i/ sytuację mieszkaniową?*

Value	Label
1	Posiadam własny dom/mieszkanie
2	Wynajmuję
3	Mieszkam u rodziny/przyjaciół
4	Inne

inc_alt

Question: *Oto lista dochodów rozporządzalnych („na rękę”). Chcielibyśmy wiedzieć, w której grupie znajduje się Pana/i/ gospodarstwo domowe przy uwzględnieniu wszystkich źródeł dochodów (m.in. zarobków, pensji, emerytur i innych) wszystkich jego członków. W przybliżeniu MIESIĘCZNIE A Poniżej 2481 PLN miesięcznie B Między 2481 - 4006 PLN miesięcznie C Między 4007 - 5532 PLN miesięcznie D Między 5533 - 6351 PLN miesięcznie E Między 6352 - 7170 PLN miesięcznie F Między 7171 - 8212 PLN miesięcznie G Między 82...*

Value	Label
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1	A) Poniżej 2481 PLN miesięcznie
2	B) Między 2481 - 4006 PLN miesięcznie
3	C) Między 4007 - 5532 PLN miesięcznie
4	D) Między 5533 - 6351 PLN miesięcznie
5	E) Między 6352 - 7170 PLN miesięcznie
6	F) Między 7171 - 8212 PLN miesięcznie
7	G) Między 8213 - 9255 PLN miesięcznie
8	H) Między 9256 - 12 531 PLN miesięcznie
9	I) Między 12 532 - 15 807 PLN miesięcznie
10	J) Powyżej 15 808 PLN miesięcznie

Populist Attitudes: People-Centrism

Czy zgadza się Pan/i/ czy też nie zgadza się z następującymi stwierdzeniami?

Scale: 1 = Zdecydowanie się nie zgadzam, 2 = Nie zgadzam się, 3 = Ani się zgadzam, ani się nie zgadzam, 4 = Zgadza się, 5 = Zdecydowanie się zgadzam. Prefer not to answer was offered but excluded from export.

Variable	Item
peoplec_pre_1	Politycy powinni zawsze uważnie wsluchiwać się w problemy ludzi.
peoplec_pre_2	Politycy nie muszą spędzać czasu wśród zwykłych ludzi, aby dobrze wykonywać swoją pracę.
peoplec_pre_3	Wola społeczeństwa powinna być najwyższą zasadą w polityce tego kraju.

Populist Attitudes: Anti-Elitism

Czy zgadza się Pan/i/ czy też nie zgadza się z następującymi stwierdzeniami?

Scale: 1 = Zdecydowanie się nie zgadzam, 2 = Nie zgadzam się, 3 = Ani się zgadzam, ani się nie zgadzam, 4 = Zgadza się, 5 = Zdecydowanie się zgadzam. Prefer not to answer was offered but excluded from export.

Variable	Item
antie_pre_1	Rząd jest w dużej mierze zarządzany przez kilka dużych grup interesu, które dbają tylko o siebie.
antie_pre_2	Urzednicy państwowi wykorzystują swoją władzę, aby poprawić jakość życia ludzi.
antie_pre_3	Sporo osób kierujących rządem jest nieuczciwych.

Populist Attitudes: Manicheanism

Czy zgadza się Pan/i/ czy też nie zgadza się z następującymi stwierdzeniami?

Scale: 1 = Zdecydowanie się nie zgadzam, 2 = Nie zgadzam się, 3 = Ani się zgadzam, ani się nie zgadzam, 4 = Zgadza się, 5 = Zdecydowanie się zgadzam. Prefer not to answer was offered but excluded from export.

Variable	Item
manich_pre_1	Można stwierdzić, czy dana osoba jest dobra czy zła, jeśli pozna się jej poglądy polityczne.
manich_pre_2	Ludzie, z którymi nie zgadzam się politycznie, nie są źli.
manich_pre_3	Ludzie, z którymi nie zgadzam się politycznie, są po prostu źle poinformowani.

Trust in Institutions (Feeling Thermometer)

Jak ocenia Pan/i/ następujące grupy i organizacje? Oceny od 50 do 100 stopni oznaczają, że ma Pan/i/ przychylne i ciepłe uczucia wobec danej grupy lub organizacji. Oceny od 0 do 50 stopni oznaczają, że ma Pan/i/ negatywne odczucia wobec tej grupy/organizacji. Jeśli nie żywi Pan/i/ wobec danej grupy lub organizacji ani ciepłych ani zimnych uczuć, proszę ją ocenić na poziomie 50 stopni. Jeśli nie rozpoznaje Pan/i grupy lub instytucji, proszę kliknąć „wolę nie odpowiadać”.

Scale: 0–100 feeling thermometer (0 = cold/unfavorable, 50 = neutral, 100 = warm/favorable). Prefer not to answer was offered but excluded from export.

Variable	Item
th_pre_1	Prasa
th_pre_4	Naukowcy
th_pre_5	Profesorowie uniwersyteccy
th_pre_6	Urzędy administracji państwowej
th_pre_7	Sejm
th_pre_8	Unia Europejska
th_pre_9	Partie polityczne
th_pre_10	Największe firmy
th_pre_11	Kapitałiści
th_pre_12	Policja
th_pre_13	Wojsko
th_pre_16	Kościół
th_pre_17	Organizacja Traktatu Północnoatlantyckiego (NATO)
th_pre_18	Międzynarodowy Fundusz Walutowy (MFW)

Nationalism

Niektórzy ludzie twierdzą, że następujące sprawy są ważne, aby być prawdziwym Polakiem. Inni mówią, że nie są one ważne. Jak ważna jest, według Pana/i/, każda z następujących spraw?

Scale: 1 = w ogóle nieważne, 2 = raczej nieważne, 3 = raczej ważne, 4 = bardzo ważne. Prefer not to answer was offered but excluded from export.

Variable	Item
nat_pre_1	Urodzenie się w Polsce
nat_pre_2	Polskie pochodzenie
nat_pre_3	Umiejętność mówienia po polsku
nat_pre_4	Korzystanie z polskiej kultury

Attitudes Towards Democracy

dem_pre

Question: *Jak bardzo ważne jest dla Pan/i/, żeby kraj w którym Pan/i/ mieszka był rządzony w sposób demokratyczny? Proszę określić Pana/i/ opinię na skali, na której 1 oznacza “zupełnie nieważne”, a 10 “zdecydowanie ważne”.*

Value	Label
1	zupełnie nieważne
2–9	(...)
10	zdecydowanie ważne

Opiszę teraz różne typy systemów politycznych. Proszę powiedzieć, co Pan/i/ myśli o każdym z nich jako o sposobie rządzenia naszym krajem.

Scale: 1 = bardzo dobry, 2 = raczej dobry, 3 = raczej zły, 4 = bardzo zły. Prefer not to answer was offered but excluded from export.

Variable	Item
polsys_pre_1	Władza silnego przywódcy, który nie musi liczyć się z parlamentem i wyborcami
polsys_pre_2	Władza ekspertów z kręgów pozarządowych, którzy przy podejmowaniu decyzji kierują się tym, co ich zdaniem jest najlepsze dla kraju
polsys_pre_3	Demokratyczny system polityczny
polsys_pre_4	Rządy wojskowych

Political Orientation and Ideology

ideol_self

Question: *Dyskutując o polityce, ludzie mówią o “lewicy” i “prawicy”. Gdzie Pan/i/ umieścił/a/by swoje poglądy na tej skali?*

Value	Label
1	lewica
2–9	(...)
10	prawica

ideol_respo

Question: *W którym miejscu na tej skali umieścić/a/by Pan/i/ swoje poglądy?*

Value	Label
1	Konkurencja jest rzeczą dobrą
2–9	(...)
10	Państwo powinno troszczyć się o zaspokojenie potrzeb wszystkich swych obywateli

ideol_eq

Question: *W którym miejscu na tej skali umieścić/a/by Pan/i/ swoje poglądy?*

Value	Label
1	Prywatna własność zakładów przemysłowych i innych przedsiębiorstw powinna być rozszerzona
2–9	(...)
10	Dochody w większym stopniu powinny nagradzać indywidualny wysiłek

ideol_own

Question: *W którym miejscu na tej skali umieścić/a/by Pan/i/ swoje poglądy?*

Value	Label
1	Prywatna własność zakładów przemysłowych i innych przedsiębiorstw powinna być rozszerzona
2–9	(...)
10	Państwowa własność zakładów przemysłowych i innych przedsiębiorstw powinna być rozszerzona

eu

Question: *Niektórzy uważają, że Unia Europejska powinna nadal się rozszerzać. Inni mówią, że już obecnie rozszerzenie zaszło za daleko. Która liczba najlepiej charakteryzuje Pana/i/ pogląd w tej sprawie. "1" oznacza "Unia Europejska powinna nadal się rozszerzać", "10" oznacza "rozszerzanie Unii Europejskiej zaszło za daleko".*

Value	Label
1	Unia Europejska powinna nadal się rozszerzać
2–9	(...)
10	Rozszerzanie Unii Europejskiej zaszło za daleko

Authoritarian Attitudes

Jak bardzo zgadza się lub nie zgadza Pan/i/ z poniższymi stwierdzeniami?

Scale: 1 = Zdecydowanie się nie zgadzam, 2 = Nie zgadzam się, 3 = Ani się zgadzam, ani się nie zgadzam, 4 = Zgadzam się, 5 = Zdecydowanie się zgadzam. Prefer not to answer was offered but excluded from export.

Variable	Item
al_1	Dzisiejsi młodzi ludzie nie mają wystarczającego szacunku dla tradycyjnych wartości
al_2	W przypadku niektórych przestępstw, kara śmierci jest najbardziej odpowiednią karą
al_3	Szkoły powinny uczyć dzieci posłuszeństwa wobec autorytetów

Political Mobilization

Poniżej wymienione są różne formy działania politycznego. O każdej z nich proszę powiedzieć, czy uczestniczył/a/ Pan/i/ w którejś z nich, czy mógł/a/by Pan/i/ wziąć w nich udział, czy raczej nigdy by Pan/i/ tego nie zrobił/a/?

Scale: 1 = uczestniczyłem/am, 2 = mógł/a/bym to zrobić, 3 = nigdy bym tego nie zrobił/a. Prefer not to answer was offered but excluded from export.

Variable	Item
mobi_1	uczestniczyłem/am
mobi_2	przyłączenie się do bojkotu
mobi_4	udział w legalnych demonstracjach
mobi_6	udział w strajku

Political Interest and Voting

pol_i

Question: *Czy interesuje się Pan/i/ polityką czy też nie?*

Value	Label
1	bardzo się interesuję
2	raczej tak
3	raczej nie
4	w ogóle się nie interesuję

pol_vote

Question: *Gdyby jutro odbyły się wybory parlamentarne, na którą partię z poniższej listy by Pan/i/ zagłosował/a/?*

Respondents who select “Other” are prompted to provide an open-text response, stored in `pol_vote_5_TEXT`.

Value	Label
1	Koalicja Obywatelska (KO)
2	Konfederacja Wolność i Niepodległość (Konfederacja)
3	Lewica
4	Trzecia Droga
5	Prawo i Sprawiedliwość (PiS)

Satisfaction and Alienation

sat

Question: *Biorąc wszystko pod uwagę, na ile jest Pan/i/ zadowolony/a/ ostatnio ze swojego życia?*

Value	Label
1	niezadowolony/a
2–9	(...)
10	zadowolony/a

alien

Question: *Niektórzy ludzie uważają, że mają całkowicie wolny wybór i w pełni kontrolują sposób, w jaki układa się im życie, inni czują, że to co robią, nie ma żadnego realnego wpływu na to, co im się przydarza. Używając tej skali - na której 1 oznacza brak wpływu a 10 oznacza maksymalny wpływ - proszę powiedzieć jak Pan/i/ ocenia swoje możliwości swobodnego układania sobie życia.*

Value	Label
1	w ogóle nie mam wpływu
2–9	(...)
10	w bardzo dużym stopniu mam wpływ

cap

Question: *W jakim stopniu zgadza się Pan/i/ lub nie zgadza się z poniższym stwierdzeniem? W moim codziennym życiu mam bardzo mało okazji do pokazania, jaki/a jestem zdolny/a.*

Value	Label
1	Zdecydowanie się nie zgadzam
2	Nie zgadzam się
3	Ani się zgadzam, ani się nie zgadzam
4	Zgadzam się

5	Zdecydowanie się zgadzam
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Neighborhood Conditions

Jak często w Pana/i/ sąsiedztwie występują następujące zjawiska?

Scale: 1 = Bardzo często, 2 = Często, 3 = Czasami, 4 = Rzadko, 5 = Nigdy. Prefer not to answer was offered but excluded from export.

Variable	Item
hood_1	Rozboje
hood_2	Spożywanie alkoholu na ulicach
hood_3	Policja ingeruje w życie prywatne ludzi

Economic Perceptions

econ

Question: *Co Pan/i/ sądzi o obecnym stanie gospodarki w Polsce? Czy powiedział/a/by Pan/i/, że stan gospodarki jest dobry, ani dobry, ani zły, czy zły?*

Value	Label
1	Dobry
2	Ani dobry, ani zły
3	Zły

econg

Question: *Jak dobry jest według Pana/i/ stan gospodarki?*

Display logic: Displayed if econ = 1 (respondent said economy is good).

Value	Label
1	Dość dobry
2	Bardzo dobry
3	Wyjątkowo dobry

econb

Question: *Jak zły jest według Pana/i/ stan gospodarki?*

Display logic: Displayed if econ = 3 (respondent said economy is bad).

Value	Label
1	Dość zły

2	Bardzo zły
3	Wyjątkowo zły

fsit

Question: *Jeśli chodzi o Pana/iq/ i Pana/i/ rodzinę, jak bardzo martwi się Pan/i/ swoją obecną sytuacją finansową?*

Value	Label
1	W ogóle
2	Trochę
3	Umiarkowanie
4	Bardzo
5	Wyjątkowo

Sexual Harassment Attitudes**harass**

Question: *Czy uważa Pan/i/, że uwaga poświęcona kwestii molestowania seksualnego posunęła się za daleko, nie posunęła się wystarczająco daleko, czy jest odpowiednia?*

Value	Label
1	Posunęła się za daleko
2	Jest odpowiednia
3	Nie posunęła się wystarczająco daleko

harass2

Question: *Czy uważa Pan/i/, że uwaga poświęcona kwestii molestowaniu seksualnemu posunęła się trochę za daleko, czy o wiele za daleko?*

Display logic: Displayed if harass = 1 (respondent said attention has gone too far).

Value	Label
1	Posunęła się trochę za daleko
2	Posunęła się o wiele za daleko

harass3

Question: *Czy uważa Pan/i/, że uwaga poświęcana kwestii molestowania seksualnego powinna być trochę czy o wiele większa?*

Display logic: Displayed if harass = 3 (respondent said attention has not gone far enough).

Value	Label
-------	-------

1	powinna być o wiele większa
2	powinna być trochę większa

Immigration and Ethnic Relations

methnic

Question: *Czy wzrost liczby osób różnych ras i grup etnicznych sprawia, że Polska staje się lepszym miejscem do życia, gorszym miejscem do życia, czy też nie robi to żadnej różnicy?*

Value	Label
1	Lepszym
2	Nie robi różnicy
3	Gorszym

methnic2

Question: *Czy wzrost liczby osób różnych ras i grup etnicznych sprawia, że Polska staje się trochę lepszym, czy też dużo lepszym miejscem do życia?*

Display logic: Displayed if methnic = 1 (respondent said diversity makes country better).

Value	Label
1	Trochę lepszym
2	Dużo lepszym

methnic3

Question: *Czy wzrost liczby osób różnych ras i grup etnicznych sprawia, że Polska staje się trochę gorszym, czy dużo gorszym miejscem do życia?*

Display logic: Displayed if methnic = 3 (respondent said diversity makes country worse).

Value	Label
1	Trochę gorszym
2	Dużo gorszym

COVID-19 and Vaccination

cov

Question: *Czy chorował/a Pan/i na COVID-19 w latach 2020-2022?*

Value	Label
1	Tak
2	Nie

vac

Question: *Czy został/a Pan/i zaszczepiony/a przeciwko COVID-19?*

Value	Label
1	Tak
2	Nie

die

Question: *Czy ktoś z Pana/i rodziny zmarł bezpośrednio w wyniku COVID-19 w latach 2020-2022?*

Value	Label
1	Tak
2	Nie

die2

Question: *Ilu członków Pana/i rodziny zmarło bezpośrednio w wyniku COVID-19 w latach 2020-2022?*

Display logic: Displayed if die = 1 (respondent said yes, a family member died of COVID).

Value	Label
1	1
2	2
3	3
4	4
5	5
6	Więcej niż 5

vacrisk

Question: *Czy korzyści zdrowotne wynikające ze szczepień ogólnie przewyższają ryzyko, czy ryzyko przewyższa korzyści, czy też nie ma różnicy?*

Value	Label
1	Korzyści przewyższają ryzyko
2	Ryzyko przewyższa korzyści
3	Bez różnicy

vacrisk2

Question: *Czy korzyści zdrowotne związane ze szczepieniami są dużo większe, czy trochę większe?*

Display logic: Displayed if vacrisk = 1 (respondent said benefits outweigh risks).

Value	Label
1	Dużo większe
2	Trochę większe

vacrisk3

Question: *Czy ryzyko związane ze szczepieniami jest dużo większe, czy trochę większe?*

Display logic: Displayed if vacrisk = 2 (respondent said risks outweigh benefits).

Value	Label
1	Dużo większe
2	Trochę większe

covsci

Question: *Ogólnie rzecz biorąc, jak ważna powinna być nauka przy podejmowaniu decyzji rządowych dotyczących COVID-19?*

Value	Label
1	W ogóle nieważna
2	Trochę ważna
3	Umiarkowanie ważna
4	Bardzo ważna
5	Wyjątkowo ważna

covforce

Question: *Niektórzy uważają, że szczepienie przeciwko COVID-19 powinno być prawnie wymagane. Inni uważają, że jednostki powinny mieć możliwość wyboru, czy chcą się zaszczepić, czy nie. Która opinia jest Panu/i/ bliższa?*

Value	Label
1	Każdy powinien być zaszczepiony
2	Każdy powinien sam zdecydować czy się zaszczepić

Niektórzy uważają, że rząd powinien karać osoby, które nie chcą się zaszczepić. Inni są temu przeciwni.

Scale: 1 = Zdecydowanie popieram, 2 = Raczej popieram, 3 = Ani nie popieram, ani się nie sprzeciwiam, 4 = Raczej się sprzeciwiam, 5 = Zdecydowanie się sprzeciwiam. Prefer not to answer was offered but excluded from export.

Variable	Item
covpen_1	Kara finansowa / grzywna
covpen_2	Jeden miesiąc pozbawienia wolności
covpen_3	Tymczasowe odebranie opieki nad dziećmi
covpen_4	Utrata pracy

Social Class

The social class variables in this survey are based on Erik Olin Wright's class analysis framework. Respondents are classified according to their position in relations of production, with employees subdivided by authority over other workers and possession of scarce skills or credentials. The questions follow a branching structure: all respondents who are currently employed (socecon = 1, 2, or 3) receive the class battery. All respondents, regardless of employment status, are asked about subjective class identification (class_self).

class

Question: *Czy jest Pan/i zatrudniony/a przez kogoś innego, pracuje na własny rachunek lub pracuje bez wynagrodzenia we własnej/rodzinnej firmie?*

Display logic: Displayed if socecon = 1, 2, or 3 (respondent is currently employed full-time, part-time, or self-employed).

Value	Label
1	Zatrudniony/a przez kogoś innego
2	Pracuję na własny rachunek
3	Pracuję bez wynagrodzenia

class_sect

Question: *Czy jest Pan/i/ zatrudniony/a/ w:*

Display logic: Displayed if class = 1 (respondent is employed by someone else).

Value	Label
1	instytucji rządowej lub publicznej
2	prywatnej firmie
3	organizacji pozarządowej

class_own

Question: *Czy jest Pan/i właścicielem lub współwłaścicielem tej firmy?*

Display logic: Displayed if class_sect = 2 (private sector), class = 2 (self-employed), or class = 3 (works without pay).

Value	Label
-------	-------

1	tak
2	nie

class_own2

Question: *Czy jest Pan/i partnerem w tej firmie lub posiada akcje?*

Display logic: Displayed if class_own = 1 (respondent is an owner or part-owner).

Value	Label
1	Tylko posiadam akcje
2	Faktyczny właściciel / partner

class_emp

Question: *Czy w tej firmie są jacyś inni płatni pracownicy? To znaczy osoby spoza rodziny, które pracują za wynagrodzenie?*

Display logic: Displayed if class = 2 (self-employed) or class = 3 (works without pay).

Value	Label
1	tak
2	nie

class_emp_no

Question: *Ilu pracowników ma/miał/a/ Pan/i/?*

Display logic: Displayed if class_own2 = 2 (actual owner/partner) or class_emp = 1 (business has paid employees).

Value	Label
1	żadnego
2	1-24
3	25 lub więcej

class_skill

Question: *Gdyby miało ukazać się ogłoszenie dotyczące Pana/i pracy, jaki byłby minimalny poziom wykształcenia lub wykszolenia wymagany do jej wykonywania?*

Display logic: Displayed if socecon = 1, 2, or 3 (respondent is currently employed).

Value	Label
1	Bez kwalifikacji
2	Wykształcenie średnie

3	50 lub więcej godzin szkolenia zawodowego
4	Wykształcenie wyższe (licencjat) lub policealne
5	Wykształcenie wyższe (magister lub doktor) lub inne dodatkowe kwalifikacje wymagane po ukończeniu studiów licencjackich

class_sup

Question: *Czy do Pana/i/ obowiązków należy kierowanie pracą innych zatrudnionych?*

Display logic: Displayed if class = 1 (respondent is employed by someone else).

Value	Label
1	tak
2	nie

class_man

Question: *Kolejne pytanie dotyczy kształtowania polityki w miejscu pracy, czyli podejmowania decyzji dotyczących takich kwestii jak dostarczane produkty lub usługi, łączna liczba zatrudnionych osób, budżety itp.*

Display logic: Displayed if class = 1 (respondent is employed by someone else).

Value	Label
1	tak
2	nie

Display logic: Displayed if class_sup = 1 (respondent supervises other employees).

Czy w ramach swojej pracy jest Pan/i/ bezpośrednio odpowiedzialny/a/ za którekolwiek z poniższych zadań?

Scale: 1 = tak, 2 = nie. Prefer not to answer was offered but excluded from export.

Variable	Item
class_sup2_2	Czy ma Pan/i wpływ na przyznanie podwyżki lub awansu podwładnemu?
class_sup2_3	Czy ma Pan/i wpływ na zwolnienie lub zawieszenie podwładnego?

class_self

Question: *Ludzie czasami opisują siebie jako należących do klasy niższej, robotniczej, średniej lub wyższej. Do której klasy by się Pan/i zaliczył/a?*

Value	Label
1	Klasa wyższa

2	Klasa średnia
3	Klasa robotnicza
4	Klasa niższa

Display logic: Displayed if class_man = 1 (respondent participates in policy-making decisions).

Czy w ramach swojej pracy uczestniczy Pan/i w którymkolwiek z poniższych rodzajów podejmowania decyzji? Obejmuje to również udzielanie porad w tym zakresie.

Scale: 1 = tak, 2 = nie. Prefer not to answer was offered but excluded from export.

Variable	Item
class_man2_1	Decyzje o zwiększeniu lub zmniejszeniu całkowitej liczby osób zatrudnionych w miejscu, w którym Pan/i pracuje?
class_man2_2	Decyzje dotyczące budżetu w miejscu, w którym Pan/i pracuje?